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**EFFECTIVENESS OF A Pedometer-based Physical Activity Program
ON BLOOD PRESSURE CONTROL AMONG ADULTS WITH HYPERTENSION IN
A TERTIARY HOSPITAL IN QUEZON CITY, PHILIPPINES**

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January 2023

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EFFECTIVENESS OF A PEDOMETER-BASED PHYSICAL ACTIVITY PROGRAM ON BLOOD PRESSURE CONTROL AMONG ADULTS WITH HYPERTENSION IN A TERTIARY HOSPITAL IN QUEZON CITY, PHILIPPINES

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Mary Lorelei Fero-Macazo, January 2023

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Acceptance Page

This Thesis titled: “EFFECTIVENESS OF A PEDOMETER-BASED PHYSICAL ACTIVITY PROGRAM ON BLOOD PRESSURE CONTROL AMONG ADULTS WITH HYPERTENSION IN A TERTIARY HOSPITAL IN QUEZON CITY, PHILIPPINES” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Arts in Nursing.

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For I know the plans I have for you,” declares the Lord, “plans to prosper you and not to harm you, plans to give you hope and a future. Then you will call on me and come and pray to me, and I will listen to you. You will seek me and find me when you seek me with all your heart. Jeremiah 29:11-12 (NIV). All praises unto God Almighty.

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DEDICATION

It is with pride that I dedicate this achievement to my father and mother, Mr. and Mrs. Victorino de Leon Macazo Sr; who with love and effort have accompanied me in this process, full of encouragement and continued prayers.

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The consummation of this Thesis study is heart fully dedicated to you.

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of the study is to determine the effectiveness of a pedometer-based walking program as a physical activity towards blood pressure control among adults with hypertension who are employed in a tertiary hospital. The study employed a quasi-experimental design, specifically a one-group before-after design wherein the dependent variable (i.e., blood pressure) was measured before (i.e., pretest) and after the intervention (i.e., posttest). Measures used in the pretest and the posttest are the same, and changes in the dependent variable from pretest to posttest are interpreted to reflect the changes brought by the intervention (pedometer-based physical activity program). There was a total of 39 participants that participated in the program, most of them are male adults with history of hypertension, have smoking habits, and some have diabetes mellitus. Study shows significant increase in blood pressure control among adults with Hypertension in the Pedometer-Based Physical Activity program as compared to those who were not. The use of pedometer is a factor that helped them continue the program and achieve the goal of 10,000 steps since they were able to track their progress. A pedometer-based walking program with daily tracking, is effective in promoting walking and improving positive affect of blood pressure control among patients with hypertension.

Keywords: Pedometer, Hypertension, Effectiveness, Physical Activity

Chapter I

THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Background of the Study

Given its reputation as a silent killer and the rising social and economic threat it poses, particularly to developing nations, hypertension is acknowledged globally as a health problem. According to estimates from the World Health Organization, 1.56 billion persons globally are expected to suffer from hypertension by the year 2025. The estimated figures indicate a prevalence of over 24% of hypertension in economically developed countries and 80% in developing countries.

In the United States, approximately one in two (46%) persons suffer from hypertension, according to the 2021 Heart Disease and Stroke Statistics. Only two-thirds of individuals with HTN are aware of it, despite its high incidence. The fact that just 25% of people have controlled blood pressure is even more startling. Asians, Hispanics, and Blacks have lower control rates than do White people. The incidence of hypertension in the Philippines rose to 37% in 2021, indicating a "progressive rise" in the country's high blood pressure population. 37% hypertension prevalence is the highest recorded since 1992. According to the survey, 72% of seniors had hypertension, compared to 5% of teenagers or those between the ages of 12 and 18. According to the Philippine Heart Association (PHA), adult and adolescent hypertensives had greater central obesity rates, waist circumferences, and BMIs (body mass index). The national incidence of hypertension among Filipino adults (20 years of age and older) has dramatically increased, according to the Food Nutrition Research Institute (FNRI), following a fall in 2013 from 22.3% to 23.9% in 2015. The Department of Health also disclosed that, in the Philippines, hypertension continues to be the primary cause of disease and is one of the variables that have been found to precipitate early mortality.

Filipinos continue to have disproportionately high rates of hypertension when compared to other racial and ethnic minority groups. As little research on cardiovascular disease risk factors had been done among Filipinos, it is likely that the country's population is more susceptible to hypertension due to a number of potential risk factors, including low levels of high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol, high rates of smoking and physical inactivity, and high body mass index (BMI) (Ursula et al., 2016). Unhealthy diets (rich in trans- and saturated fat, high in salt, low in fruits and vegetables), physical inactivity, alcohol and tobacco use, and being overweight or obese are examples of modifiable risk factors. Risk factors that cannot be changed include age over 65, a family history of hypertension, and co-occurring conditions like diabetes or renal illness (WHO, 2019).

Blood pressure control remains poor among adult Filipinos despite the significant advancements in the understanding of hypertension and the availability of effective treatment strategies (Abarquez et al., 2000). If control were suboptimal, it would then be logical to direct strategy at the preventive level to control disease occurrence (Faraco & Ladecola, 2013). Hence, as an adult, it is very important to know your blood pressure level, adhere to pharmacologic treatment, regular medical checkup and commit to lifestyle modification.

Our capacity to move as we age might be greatly impacted by this lifestyle, which can lower our overall quality of life. According to a recent Movement Today poll, Filipinos have not moved as much since the epidemic began. The poll, which was conducted in the third quarter of 2021, sought to determine how Filipinos' levels of physical activity had evolved over the previous 12 months. The people who participated in the research ranged in age from 20 to 50. Sixty-seven percent of the 293 respondents overall stated they felt less active since the COVID-19 outbreak began. You don't need to spend much, if anything,

on transportation. Dr. Li-Yu, an orthopedic doctor, claims that walking is a beneficial activity for the whole body.

Similarly, the United States Physical Activity Guidelines Committee Scientific Report emphasized the possible advantages of expressing and quantifying physical activity volume in terms of steps taken per day. The rationale behind this metric is that it is easily comprehensible by the general public and can be helpful in tracking individual physical activity objectives when paired with modern, widely available wearable technologies. Wearable technology such as pedometer-based programs has elicited increased walking behaviors associated with improvements in blood pressure in sedentary adult populations at increased risk of cardiovascular disease (Dela Cruz et.al., 2018). A program like this usually promotes increasing physical activity levels without giving much thought to intensity. The meta-analysis's findings suggest that walking with a pedometer can lower blood pressure since it should be careful of boosting step count rather than daily step count (JHH, 2018).

Walking, i.e., achieving 10,000 steps/day, as the major intervention in the study is linked with reduced cardiovascular risk, morbidity, and mortality in patients with various categories of hypertension. Furthermore, reduced time spent being sedentary has a significant cardiovascular effect. The predicted risk of experiencing a myocardial infarction or coronary death increases by one percent for every 25 to 30 minutes that an individual is sedentary (Fritzgerald et al., 2017). Studies have shown the positive impact of electronic and modern health technologies in promoting physical activity. These results should motivate medical professionals and families to assist individuals in establishing a healthy lifestyle (Fletcher, 2018).

Statement of the Problem

Realizing the country's constraint in mitigating the high prevalence of hypertension, the researcher commits to deepening the understanding of hypertension control through disease prevention and health promotion with physical activity. Across the world, there are substantial but missed opportunities in promoting health for adult persons with hypertension using low-level exercise. Establishing new and innovative ways to control hypertension needs to be explored.

In its effort to mitigate the COVID-19 pandemic, the Philippines has implemented community quarantine protocols across the country. This has limited the social mobility of many Filipinos, thereby increasing the number of adults who are physically inactive. Workplaces are key settings to implement cost-effective, efficient behavioral physical activity programs to increase physical activity. In the Philippines, there are fewer studies about physical activity using walking steps (Pedometer Use) and its outcome on blood pressure (BP) control among adults with Hypertension in a hospital setting, hence this study.

Adults with hypertension who engage in physical exercise had lower systolic and diastolic blood pressure. The use of wearable technologies such as pedometers has a potential positive impact on the physical activity of adults as they can self-monitor or self-regulate their progress in terms of daily steps achieved. This study also seeks to determine the association of pedometers to blood pressure control and behavior of promoting physical activity among adult employees.

Objectives of the Study

The primary goal of the research is to ascertain if a walking program based on pedometers is beneficial for controlling blood pressure in persons with hypertension who work in tertiary hospitals as a form of physical exercise. This study specifically seeks to:

1. Describe the demographic and clinical characteristics of adults with hypertension.
2. Determine if there is a significant difference in Blood Pressure Control across four measurements.
3. Determine the association between the use of wearable technology for blood pressure control (pedometer) and health-promoting behavior (self-regulation) among adults with hypertension.

Significance of the Study

The rapidly increasing prevalence of hypertension among the adult population aged 20 and older in the country, and the poor control of disease progression and emergence of complications show that the current health strategies for hypertension in the Philippines is suboptimal. Hence, there is a need to explore other effective interventions for managing the risk factors of hypertension.

The health care system in many countries is moving towards innovative technologies for patients with chronic non-communicable diseases, which can later be life-threatening illnesses. This technology can be an avenue in reaching optimal blood pressure control aimed toward cardiovascular health promotion, readmission prevention, health restoration and rehabilitation among adults with hypertension. Promoting physical activity is important to combat the unprecedented rise in non-communicable diseases (NCDs) in many developing countries.

It is necessary to investigate novel approaches to reaching these goals in sedentary communities. Given the growing number of pedometers on the market, utilizing contemporary information and communication technology to promote physical activity is very promising (Alley et al., 2016). To determine whether daily pedometer usage may promote physical activity and improve blood pressure control, improvements should be continuously observed and reevaluated after adhering to physical activity with walking steps (Cheng et al., 2009).

During the acute phase of the illness and the recovery period, physical inactivity can have a detrimental effect on emotional state and even result in total loss of interest and activity. Even a short-term program lasting for four (4) weeks can be accompanied by controlled blood pressure and positive health perception. Pedometer-based programs, either used as a motivational tool or combined with medical professional advice, were found to be more cost-saving and more effective compared to the usual intervention: oral or written advice to perform the exercise by a medical professional (Lewis et al., 2010). This was in line with the results of a systematic review conducted by Abu-Omar et al. (2017), which showed that pedometer-based treatments to promote adult physical activity were shown to be cost-effective. Evaluating the relative costs and advantages of new treatment programs has become more crucial in an era of healthcare reform and cost management for medical expenses.

This study finds its relevance to the following:

1. Clinical Nursing Practice: Innovations in wearable technology are revolutionizing healthcare, distributing responsibility to patients, and ultimately resulting in self-care (Appelboom et al., 2014). Nurses can expand the application of nursing practice and better serve the sedentary population who may benefit from these products knowing the capabilities and platforms of wearable technology. This will empower the future of

nursing, facing the rapid influx of healthcare technology aimed at hastening individual, family and community collaborative participation in the treatment regimen, lifestyle changes and wellness.

2. Nursing Management: The practice of professional nursing, both now and in the future, is greatly influenced by administration. It is essential to the nursing profession and required for ongoing development in order to provide the best possible nursing care. Effective, empathetic, and patient-centered care is what nurses strive to provide. Good research is crucial in determining what approaches to healthcare delivery are most effective, as well as where and with whom they work best.
3. Nursing Academe: Nursing educators can empower nursing students to learn new healthcare technologies that can mobilize and help patients in performing self-care. Nurses should capitalize on the wearable technology industry through being visionary and proactive. With the influx of emerging technology, educators are encouraged to provide motivation and positive stimulus to students in revolutionizing the application of healthcare wearable technologies.
4. Nursing Research: To the future researchers, it is recommended that a follow-up study using a larger sample size be undertaken for more reliable statistical results. May this study serve as a building block in expanding innovative models of nursing theory, aimed at reaching the clients' optimal quality of life. Moreover, this will empower nurses, not just to be intelligent consumers, but also as producers of quality nursing research. This is essential in honing the knowledge, skills, and attitude of professional nurses. This will also pave the way to look at the new innovations in nursing that can assist patients as well as the nurses themselves in monitoring patients' health.

5. Allied Health Professionals: Pedometer use provides an intervention that is less intrusive and cost-effective. Clinical choices can be customized and guided by other members of the healthcare team by integrating and using recorded data from wearable technologies (pedometers). Outcome of research mobilizes health care staff and personnel in joining in the command for self-care and responsibility.
6. Hospital Administrators: This will provide up-to-date data on the physical activity of hospital employees with hypertension. This may aid in empowering and advocating for workplace health promotion and developing simple, cost-effective physical activity programs given the benefits of this behavior to health.
7. Community: Nurses must educate the target population on hypertension and blood pressure control and awareness and be able to affect change in their lifestyle by strictly adhering and maintaining adequate physical activity. Moreover, nurses will continue to provide adequate and up-to-date information that would enhance the ability to cope with chronic illness, symptom management and health care compliance.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

The objective of this research is to induce blood pressure management in individuals with hypertension at a tertiary hospital located in Quezon City, Philippines, by promoting a minimum of 7000 to 10,000 walking steps per day. The study will concentrate on the impact of a physical activity program based on pedometers on the blood pressure of people, recruited from the Philippine Heart Center staff, who range in age from 21 to 65. The entirety of the intervention is a thirty (30) day period. Participants will record daily walking steps as measured by the pedometer achieved at the end of the day (before bedtime). Moreover, the blood pressure of participants will be monitored during the weekly visit at the facility's Employee Health clinic. In order to test and assess the link between the target participants'

perceived blood pressure control and their actual clinical blood pressure in the context of clinical values, it is helpful to have access to the target participants' clinical blood pressure data.

While pedometers are regarded as a more objective way to quantify walking than self-reporting, it's crucial to exclude activities like swimming, resistance training, upper-body motions, cycling, and other complicated movements that can skew the study's findings. It is reasonable to believe that the pedometer records the majority of daily physical activity because adults often engage in moderate exercise, such walking (Al Sayah et al., 2016).

It is thought that three days will adequately capture a frequent pedometer user in populations of healthy adults. According to Rowe et al. (2009), sedentary people with chronic diseases seem to need even less days—just two days—to achieve a consistent assessment of their habitual physical activity.

The research team initiates, monitors, and foresees selections of participants, presents research objectives, participates in health education on hypertension as to prevalence, risk and treatment, administers research-related questionnaires, explains in detail how to use the pedometer and how to record walking steps on a daily manner and entertain participant concerns. Physical activity and exercise (walking) as the major interventions in this study are linked with reduced cardiovascular risk, morbidity, and mortality in adults with various categories of hypertension.

Chapter II

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

This chapter is divided into three sections. The first section presents a summary of the existing literature about this study. The second section presents the conceptual framework that served as the theoretical rationale in the analysis of the variables involved. Finally, the third section discusses the operational definition of terms commonly used throughout the study and the hypothesis.

Review of Related Literature

The review of related literature in this chapter covers local and foreign academic published studies and journal articles on low-level exercise/10,000 walking steps using a pedometer as a wearable technology, hypertension, self-care, and health promotion as it relates to blood pressure control among the adult population. Literature points to a considerable anti-hypertension benefit even with a low level of exercise.

Search engines include searches in Nursing (American Journal of Nursing, Philippine Nurses Association Publications), Medical (CINAHL, MEDLINE), PubMed and Up-to-Date electronic databases. All references include the terms “hypertension”, “physical activity”, “walk*”, “steps”, “pedometer”, “wearable tech”, or “health promotion” in the abstract.

Further hand-searched readings in university and hospital libraries involved selection of journal articles, published and unpublished abstracts, theses, meta-analysis, and dissertations for additional relevant studies. Due to the paucity of studies on the use of pedometers for blood pressure control in the Philippine context, the search was restricted to the last 15 years. Limiters were configured to contain both a complete abstract and the English language. Gray literature sourced from Google Scholar and other online resources was used for an extra search.

Through the prevention and management of hypertension, public health has significantly improved life expectancy globally over the past century. Developed nations must contend with the complicated problems of an aging population, an increase in the prevalence of chronic illnesses (such as obesity, diabetes, and hypertension), and the need to control costs in the face of new technology and growing standards. The major difficulty faced by middle-class and low-income nations is the deficiency of skilled health workers, particularly in the field of public health, as well as inadequate infrastructure and financial mechanisms. Their capacity to manage the dual burden of disease brought about by the confluence of aging populations, growing middle-class lifestyles, fast population expansion, and poverty is greatly hampered by this.

One goal for non-communicable illnesses worldwide is a 25% decrease in the incidence of hypertension by 2025. There is still much needed effort in terms of prevention and management of hypertension to achieve the said target. Hence, the WHO has launched the Global Hearts Initiative called the HEARTS technical package in 2016. There are five modules in this package mentioned as follows: (1) Healthy-lifestyle counseling, (2) Evidence-based treatment protocols, (3) Access to essential medicines and technology, (4) Team-based care and (5) Systems for monitoring. This program seeks to offer a global strategy for enhancing cardiovascular health in various nations. The Philippines is among the fifteen nations that began implementing such measures.

The Department of Health (DOH) is continuing efforts to reduce the incidence of hypertension, i.e., the promotion of healthy lifestyles, in light of the rising prevalence of disorders associated to lifestyle choices. The Philippine Heart Association, a coalition of medical societies, professional associations, academic institutions, and other government agencies, and other partners are involved in these projects. The National Healthy Lifestyle

Campaign placed a strong emphasis on controlling weight, engaging in regular physical activity, and opposing smoking.

Physical Activity

Increased physical exercise has been shown to reduce cardiovascular risk factors including hypertension. Resistance training and aerobics can lower blood pressure in hypertensive individuals, improve lipid profiles, inflammation, and body composition in overweight and obese individuals, and improve insulin sensitivity, blood glucose control, and body composition in type 2 diabetics.

Significant advancements in scientific understanding about physical activity and health have led to the development of the World Health Organization's (WHO) recommendations for physical activity and sedentary behavior (WHO, 2020). Increasing physical activity is a major public health priority that lowers the risk of cardiovascular disease. The guidelines state that a minimum of 150 minutes of moderate intensity physical activity or 75 minutes of vigorous intensity is required to achieve at least 600 metabolic equivalent tasks (MET)-minutes throughout a week, including activity for work, during transportation, and during leisure time.

They stress cutting back on sitting and substituting any amount of physical exercise. It's noteworthy that strength exercise is advised for all people on at least two days a week. The 2018 recommendations from the European Society of Cardiology and the European Society of Hypertension prescribe resistance training two to three days a week in addition to 30 minutes of moderate-intensity physical exercise five to seven days a week.

A study conducted by Choudry (2016) in Mahayag, Zamboanga del Sur seeks to determine the effect of behavioral lifestyle modification programs on the blood pressure levels of hypertensive adults. The intervention group received lecture sessions on behavioral

lifestyle modifications, house visits and *hataw* sessions, whereas the control group had one group lecture session and no *hataw* session. Results showed that blood pressure positively improved among the former group compared to the latter.

Patients with heart failure and coronary artery disease also see a reduction in chronic inflammation after exercise. This suggests that by addressing the most common risk factors for coronary artery disease, systematic physical exercise may help prevent it. Physical activity's efficacy is probably due to its numerous beneficial impacts on cardiovascular risk factors and the biology of atherosclerosis. According to Alves (2016), who wrote an editorial for the Archives of Exercise in Health and Disease, "Physical Activity and Coronary Artery Disease: Looking beyond risk factors," patients with coronary artery disease who engage in regular physical activity have improved myocardial perfusion and decreased endothelial dysfunction and arterial stiffness. There is evidence that when organized physical activity occurs, endothelial progenitor cells (EPC) are recruited from the bone marrow into endothelial injury sites. This suggests that EPC may play a role in the regeneration and repair of the injured endothelium.

Reduced long-term morbidity and death are linked to exercise. Everyone benefits from low-intensity physical exercise, including those who are at a higher risk of having unfavorable cardiovascular events. The more physical fitness and exercise, the better the health advantages, especially for those without a hereditary predisposition to cardiovascular disease or symptoms of the condition. Adults maintaining a regular routine of physical activity of longer duration are likely to have greater benefits.

In a study made in China (Qian et. al., 2000), blood pressure was positively impacted by physical activity. Lowering blood pressure at rest and preventing an excessive spike in blood pressure during physical activity are two benefits of exercise. Exercise on its own is linked to a 3.5 and 2.0 mmHg drop in SBP and DBP, respectively. In research published in

2000, Reid et al. replaced pharmaceutical blood pressure control with lifestyle management, and found that 71% of the participants could continue not taking medication and yet have well-controlled blood pressure. Additionally, it can lessen the need for, expense of, and adverse effects associated with antihypertensive medications while also enhancing health-related quality of life (HRQoL).

The main finding of an East Asian meta-analysis research assessing the benefits of consistent aerobic exercise was a decrease in systolic blood pressure, which was strongly correlated with "exercise time x exercise frequency." (Igarashi et al., 2018). In an urban Philippine community setting, the Effectiveness of Lifestyle with Diet and Physical Activity Education Program (ENLIGHTEN) aims to ascertain whether a monthly lifestyle education program that included suggestions for enhancing physical activity can effectively lower blood pressure and cause a statistically significant drop in blood pressure. These results demonstrated that lifestyle interventions may be implemented successfully, and they advocate for the introduction of education and lifestyle intervention programs in the Philippines and other developing nations with limited access to healthcare in the future (Gabiola et al., 2021).

Table 1

Health benefits associated with regular physical activity for adults

Hypertension	Lower risk of cardiovascular disease mortality Reduced cardiovascular disease progression Lower risk of increased blood pressure over time
Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus	Lower risk of cardiovascular disease mortality Reduced progression of disease indicators: hemoglobin A1c, blood pressure, body mass index and lipids
Cancer	Reduced risks of developing cancers of the colon, breast, prostate, rectum

Neuro-psychological health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced risk of dementia (including Alzheimer's disease) Improved cognition among adults older than 50 years old (executive function, attention, memory, processing speed) Reduced risk of depression Improved quality of life and decreases fatigue Improved sleep outcomes
All-cause Mortality/ Morbidity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced risk of all-cause mortality or morbidity such as hypertension
Weight management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slowed or reduced weight gain Weight loss, especially if in combination with reduced calorie intake Prevention of weight regain following initial weight loss

The aforementioned findings are encouraging because they imply that physical activity is a low-cost, efficient lifestyle tactic for raising indicators of vascular regeneration capacity, which would otherwise decline with aging and chronic vascular conditions.

However, despite the recommendations from various organizations such as WHO and the Department of Health (DOH) on regular physical activity, high proportions of physical inactivity are still observed over the past years among Filipino adults. The importance of physical activity is still underestimated, despite its many advantages. Worldwide, physical inactivity is still quite common, and cardiac rehabilitation program adherence is considerably lower than one may anticipate. The issue of compliance with long-term physical activity regimens is another that need attention.

Increasing aerobic exercise training (ET) has been advised by several organizations, such as the American Heart Association and the American College of Sports Medicine, in order to raise the general population's levels of cardiorespiratory fitness (CRF). Performance during aerobic exertion is influenced by factors such as age, sex, and genetic predispositions that affect the physiological response. Though every system—neurologic, pulmonary, respiratory, musculoskeletal, and cardiovascular—that plays a role in

coordinating a suitable reaction to aerobic exercise is significant, the cardiovascular system—specifically, cardiac systolic and diastolic function—can be considered the central nervous system.

According to the Center for Communicable Disease and Prevention, older adults who engage in physical exercise have lower blood pressure, which lowers their chance of dying from coronary heart disease. Exercise is recognized to be beneficial to the heart at any age. Additionally, Buford et al. (2015) reported that reduction of sedentary time could have cardiovascular benefits.

Even with significant advancements in the pharmaceutical management of hypertension, symptoms persist in a number of people. Decreased exercise capacity and a low quality of life are the results of these ailments. The evaluation of exercise training's potential benefits for improving heart function and quality of life takes this context into account. Due to its many health advantages, physical activity has been referred to as a "miracle drug." This suggests that exercise is a low-cost and effective lifestyle option for restoring indicators of vascular regeneration ability, which otherwise declines with age and chronic vascular illnesses.

Lastly, a deeper comprehension of the processes behind the benefits associated with exercise training is required in order to maximize the efficacy of exercise training programs and to identify which patients will gain the most from them.

Pedometer (Walking Steps Device Measurement)

A pedometer is a low-cost motion sensor that reacts to the hip's vertical acceleration throughout a walking cycle. It is usually worn on a belt and waist band (Sylvia et al., 2014). According to Tudor-Locke (2003), the step counter is a legitimate tracking gadget that may also be used as a feedback tool to gauge one's level of physical activity. Numerous studies

have demonstrated that this gadget considerably raises physical activity levels and is linked to lower blood pressure, body mass index, and waist circumference.

Among those who are more likely to develop cardiovascular disease, pedometer-based programs have been shown to promote walking habits and reduce blood pressure (Tudor-Locke et al., 2014). Usually, these regimens recommend moderate exercise for thirty (30) minutes (i.e., at least fifty steps per minute).

Modern commercial pedometer technology allows for the recording of daily steps taken as well as the amount of time spent engaging in moderate-to-intense physical activity. Walking every day is a low-cost exercise that would strengthen current connections and promote improved chronic illness management. The idea behind the pedometer is that it can encourage older persons to walk more and maintain a greater level of exercise, improving their functional status and potentially lowering their blood pressure.

One aerobic activity that has been suggested for the treatment of hypertension is walking (10,000 steps per day). The impact of walking on ambulatory blood pressure (BP) has not been extensively studied. This employs continuous recording on the number of steps a patient accumulates each day. Each participant wears a pedometer to accurately record and evaluate BP effect. Organized exercise is an effective, low-cost treatment and preventative measure against high blood pressure.

Yuenyongchaiwat et al. (2016) conducted a longitudinal quasi-experimental study to examine the impact of 10,000 steps per day on blood pressure and blood glucose levels in overweight adults aged 35-39. The study's findings indicated that increasing physical activity by walking more steps per day can lower blood pressure and blood glucose levels.

In a similar study conducted by Miyazaki & Kotani (2015), the researchers investigated the effect of a year-long pedometer-based walking program in older people. After analyzing

the correlation between the quantity of steps taken each day and the modifications in cardiovascular disease risks, they discovered a considerable decrease in systolic blood pressure. In conclusion, even physically active older adults can reduce their risk of CVD by engaging in mild to moderate physical activity for longer than a year by utilizing pedometers.

Bravata et al. (2007) carried out a comprehensive evaluation to assess the relationship between pedometer use and health outcomes and physical activity in people receiving outpatient care. The usage of pedometers was shown to be significantly associated with increases in physical activity as well as substantial reductions in blood pressure and body mass index. The use of a pedometer has been shown to significantly increase daily steps, and recent studies have also shown a drop in systolic blood pressure and other health outcomes including body mass index (Matthew et al., 2019).

Furthermore, Chongthawonsatid & Chijenpradit (2017) carried out a randomized control trial in Thailand to evaluate the efficacy of a supervised modified exercise program consisting of moderate-intensity exercise for one hour per week with the use of a pedometer versus the use of a pedometer alone without additional exercise in lowering blood pressure. Compared to baseline data, both groups' systolic blood pressure improved by the third and sixth months. After the intervention, both groups did not exhibit statistically significant differences, according to multiple regression analysis.

According to a randomized controlled research that was published in the Journal of Family Practice in 2017, engaging in regular physical activity (PA) lowers the risk of several chronic illnesses and has numerous positive health effects. According to international standards, participants should engage in aerobic vigorous-intensity physical activity for at least 20 minutes three times a week, or moderate-intensity physical activity for at least 30 minutes five times a week. Hatano (2017) suggested an alternative recommendation that is commonly utilized in physical activity studies, recommending at least 10,000 steps per day.

Various forms of PA treatments, including computer-tailored and pedometer-based interventions, have been created in the past to encourage individuals to attain these requirements. This trial concludes that in a year of leisure walking, blood pressure level is controlled among older participants.

The incorporation of other health promotion activities, such as tracking walking steps in a journal or website, sharing step counts with others, counseling sessions, weekly meetings, and group physical activity sessions, is associated with the effectiveness of pedometer use in changing behavior related to physical activity (Freak-Poli et al., 2020).

In the study of Wang & Boros (2020), results indicated that adding aerobic walking exercise to one's regular routine could improve one's quality of sleep. More research is recommended to determine the long-term effects of the pedometer-based daily walking exercise and to elucidate the molecular processes behind its influence on improving sleep quality.

Hypertension

Hypertension is described as unusually high arterial blood pressure by the American Heart Association (AHA). A blood pressure reading that falls between the normal (optimal) range of systolic pressure less than 120 mmHg and diastolic pressure less than 80 mmHg is considered normal. The Joint National Committee on Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure's Eighth Report classifies hypertension as prehypertension, Stages 1 and 2, and Hypertensive Crisis (www.nhlbi.nih.gov/index.htm).

Table 2*Blood pressure classification (8th Joint National Committee/JNC 8, 2017).*

Blood Pressure Category	Systolic mmHg*		Diastolic mmHg*
Normal	Less than 120	and	Less than 80
Elevated	120 – 129	and	Less than 80
High Blood Pressure (Hypertension) Stage 1	130 – 139	or	80 – 89
High Blood Pressure (Hypertension) Stage 2	140 or higher	or	90 or higher
Hypertensive Crisis	Higher than 180	and/or	Higher than 120

**Individuals with SBP and DBP in 2 categories should be designated to the higher BP category.*

In 2017, the Eighth Report of the Joint National Committee on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure provided a new guideline for hypertension prevention and management. The following are the key messages:

1. Systolic blood pressure (BP) of greater than 140 mmHg is a significantly more significant risk factor for cardiovascular disease (CVD) in those over 50 than diastolic BP;

2. Every 20/10 mm Hg increase in the risk of CVD causes it to double; those who are normotensive at age 55 have a 90% lifetime chance of developing hypertension;

3. People who have a diastolic blood pressure of 80 to 89 mmHg or a systolic blood pressure of 120 to 139 mmHg should be diagnosed as pre-hypertensive and should make lifestyle changes that promote health in order to prevent CVD;

4. Most individuals with simple hypertension should be treated with thiazide-type diuretics, either on their own or in combination with medications from other classes;

5. For the majority of hypertensive patients, two or more antihypertensive drugs are needed to reach target blood pressure (<140/90 mmHg; <130/80 mmHg in the case of diabetes or chronic renal disease);

6. Consideration should be given to starting therapy with two agents if BP is greater than 20/10 mmHg over target BP. Typically, one of the drugs should be a thiazide-type diuretic;

7. Only when patients are motivated can even the most effective medicine, provided by the most cautious doctor, be able to control hypertension.

Figure 1. Top 10 leading causes of death in the Philippines (2013)

Mortality: Ten (10) Leading Causes

This evident data is alarming and needs to be addressed by preventing these kinds of diseases, which are long in duration and generally slow in progression. Hypertension, if ignored, being a top-rated risk of developing cardiovascular diseases, the country's overall mortality will increase leading to a negative impact on our society. According to the Framingham Heart Study, there was a 90% lifetime probability of acquiring systolic hypertension by the time an individual was 80–85 years old, even if they had normal blood pressure measurements at age 65 (Franklin, 2012). As a result, as the population ages and life expectancy rises, hypertension in the elderly will become increasingly prevalent, necessitating the knowledge of medical professionals on the diagnosis, treatment, and management of this illness. It's critical to go by guidelines while taking your blood pressure. Assessing the degree to which patients understand the significance of managing their blood pressure via self-care, awareness, and ongoing health education with the help of a support group is beneficial.

Figure 2. Trend in the prevalence of hypertension among adults 20 years and above in the Philippines, 1993-2019 (DOST, FNRI).

The nationwide incidence of hypertension among Filipino individuals aged 20 and over has dramatically increased, according to the Food Nutrition Research Institute's (FNRI) 2015 study, following a fall in 2013 from 22.3% to 23.9% in 2015. Though hypertension is more common among older adults, the increasing incidence of elevated blood pressure among young adults has been observed over the past years. Prevalence of elevated blood pressure among adults by age group which was found to be significantly different at 5% level of significance were as follows: 20-29 years old (9.1%); 30-39 years old (11.7%); 40-49 years old (28.3%); 50-59 years old (36.3%). Hence, the researcher deemed it necessary to include the different adult groups: young adults, middle-aged adults, and older adults in the study.

The burden of hypertension is not peculiar to a developing country that the Philippines is. It is well recognized that the government through the Department of Health rightfully assumes responsibility for this burden. Hypertension prevalence among adults, aged 20 years and older, in the Philippines has continually increased in the past years. Data from the Food and Nutrition Research Institute of the Department of Science and Technology showed a significant increase in prevalence, from 22.3% in 2013 to 23.9% in 2015 (p -value=0.001). In addition, it's believed that at least 25% of individuals have hypertension, and for those over 60, the percentage rises to more than half (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, 2011).

Over the previous three decades, the global population with uncontrolled hypertension rose to over one (1) billion individuals. One major contributing factor to the latter's illness is hypertension. Consequently, efficient management of hypertension has emerged as a worldwide health concern. Finding out the annual death toll and the cause of death are two of the most crucial ways to evaluate the performance of a nation's healthcare system and decide on public health initiatives. According to estimates, at least 25% of individuals have hypertension, and for those over 60, the percentage rises to more than 50% (National

Institute for Health and Care Excellence/NICE, 2011). Furthermore, physical inactivity as a risk factor for hypertension was observed to be of high proportions among adults based on the FNRI National Nutrition Survey in 2018 with 45.7% among young adults aged 20-29; 40.3% among 30-39 years old; 37% among 40-49 years old; and 37.8% among 50-59 years old.

Synthesis

The commitment of nurses to health awareness is, therefore, of paramount importance. Literature strongly suggests health-promoting behaviors in the field of “Teaching”, and corroborating “Lifestyle Change” (i.e., diet, weight reduction, low level exercise, adherence to medication and follow-up consultation). This promotes wellness in various facets of patients’ health belief, clinical presentation, education, culture, and psychosocial support.

Leveraging the widespread popularity of walking as a viable lifestyle choice and the usefulness of pedometer-driven programming, 10,000 Steps is intended to assess the relative merits of augmenting ambulatory physical activity. This will support public health initiatives and provide a clear, doable walking exercise program for lowering blood pressure in a subgroup of people who are more likely to develop cardiovascular disease. Less than 5% of adults engage in the recommended amount of moderate to vigorous physical activity (i.e., 30 minutes per day) based on objectively recorded behavior, with women over 50 having the lowest prevalence.

Poor control of BP might be due to a lack of knowledge in the therapy rather than the failure of the treatment program. Patients who receive more intensive and personalized health education achieved better BP control through continuing informed lifestyle change.

Treatment of hypertension, including lifestyle interventions, can be effective for 80% to 85% of patients (Berlowitz, 2013).

This marks a tremendous challenge to us nurses to be truly diverse in working with Chronic non-communicable diseases. One of the main and most common risk factors for the development of chronic disorders is hypertension. The relative advantages of exercise (walking, depending on volume and/or intensity) for improving blood pressure control in the at-risk group can be better understood according to this study. The rigorous monitoring and measurement of the pedometer-based physical activity treatments is a significant research strength. The management of blood pressure is the main result.

Health-related quality of life, or HRQoL, is a particularly significant result in chronic disorders like hypertension since these conditions need daily self-management and are lifelong. The nurse, as a member of a multidisciplinary team, has an essential role – a call for a holistic understanding of an individual's social and cultural context, reflecting and having a critical and active attitude regarding their health. Only then can there be positive health outcomes (Figueiredo et al., 2018).

Theoretical Framework

One definition of self-regulation is a goal-guidance process that aims to achieve and sustain individual goals. To achieve task- and time-specific outcomes, this calls for the self-reflective guidance process of several change and maintenance mechanisms. One way to define goals is as mental images or ideas of desired conditions or results.

Hypertension is a silent killer. It is symptomless and the importance of adherence and continued therapy is a challenge in incorporating self-awareness in making lifestyle changes. Nursing realizes that advocacy can save lives as much as a person assesses self-understanding of his own diagnosis and incorporating treatment into daily life. The self-

regulation hypothesis emphasizes the need of planning, goal setting, and self-awareness in altering behavior. This theory seeks to assess results related to people's active engagement as agents of their own motivation, goal setting, adherence, behavior, and advancement.

Interventions for behavior modification need to be grounded in theory and driven by a decision-making process that compares the short- and long-term advantages of a certain behavior. Regardless of prior intentions, motivation to pursue a health-related objective will be reduced if the immediate expenses are high and the rewards are low. Setting goals and keeping an eye on oneself are essential for changing behavior.

Self-efficacy is one psychological aspect that is crucial to comprehending the course and treatment of any disease, as well as how patients adjust their lifestyles to cope with the condition. Self-efficacy is a psychological concept that is frequently utilized in the treatment of chronic illnesses, such as hypertension (Khairy et al., 2021). Numerous studies have revealed inadequate control of hypertension and that the key concerns in therapy are risk factor management and preventative practices. As a result, patients require a variety of techniques to improve their ability to manage their own care. A psychological notion called self-efficacy is frequently linked to the capacity to manage chronic illnesses (Hallberg et al., 2016).

It was also discovered that a substantial difference in self-efficacy was related to gender, type of habitation, work state, BMI, and educational attainment. A greater self-efficacy measure was linked to male gender and city residence. This finding contradicts the results of a 2015 Chinese study that found no significant relationship between self-efficacy and sex, but their findings regarding patients' age, marital status, and duration of hypertension were similar to ours in that there was no significant relationship between these variables and patients' self-efficacy (Hu, Li & Arao, 2015).

By comparing present behavior to the desired conduct, self-monitoring enables one to determine when changes are required. Walking is frequently less organized and salient than scheduled physical activities, thus self-monitoring walking behavior might be difficult. Nevertheless, self-monitoring tools like pedometers can help with timely and accurate self-monitoring of walking behavior. There is mounting evidence that substantial changes in behavior related to health may be effectively affected by digital interventions. Pedometers have been demonstrated to be accurate and acceptable to adults. They are also simple to use and offer feedback that has significant informative and motivating impact.

In this study, a self-regulation theory-based intervention will be paired with the use of pedometers. Bravata et al.'s 2017 systematic review established the relationship between pedometer use, physical activity, and a range of health-related outcomes. The study's conclusion was that walking-related activities might encourage inactive people to move more.

When treatments are customized to meet the requirements of the individual, people may be inspired to walk more. It has been demonstrated that the use of pedometers can improve initiatives meant to raise levels of physical activity. In a randomized controlled trial conducted among sedentary older women, findings showed that women who used the pedometer as an objective measurement of physical activity achieved their goal steps compared to their counterparts. They were able to monitor their progress and assess their goal achievement daily (Sugden et al., 2008).

Figure 3. Social Cognitive Theory of Self-regulation (Bandura, 1991)

Conceptual Framework

Figure 4. Schematic diagram showing the interrelationship of variables.

Using the Social Cognitive Theory of Self-Regulation Model of Bandura (1991) and related literature, the above conceptual framework was established as a guiding model of the study. The independent variable, also known as the intervention variable, is a lifestyle modification effort involving Physical Activity (Walking steps/day) which will be measured using a pedometer (device attached to the body). With the use of the pedometer, participants

will be able to self-monitor their progress in terms of daily steps achieved. The dependent variable, also known as the outcome variable, is the participant's blood pressure, which is monitored on a weekly basis, using the same BP apparatus located at the hospital's Employee Health Clinic. This is measured by the Nurse on duty or assigned at the Employee Health Clinic.

The population of the study aged from 21 to 65 years old, with hypertension. Participants are conveniently sampled from the list of employees at the Philippine Heart Center diagnosed with hypertension. The researcher aims to seek and evaluate physical activity in terms of escalating walking steps per day (with a goal of 10,000 steps) using a pedometer device and its effect on blood pressure over a 30-day period. This study shows how physical activity through walking exercises plays a key role in motivating hypertensive adults to begin an exercise while focusing on individual goals, concerns, and barriers to exercise. The exercise regimen should be simple, enjoyable, and tailored to the individual's self-reaction to objectives, beliefs, and health requirements in order to promote long-term compliance.

Operational Definition of Terms

The following section defines how key terms will be used in this study.

1. **Physical activity:** referred to as daily walking steps (10000 walking steps / day). The concept of reducing the amount of time you're sedentary leading to blood pressure control and health-related quality of life.
2. **Pedometer use:** usage of a battery-powered device that counts steps taken to estimate the distance covered on foot and tracks people's daily walking distance.

3. **Hypertension:** Adults over the age of 18 are considered to have hypertension if their sustained SBP is 140 mmHg or higher, or if their DBP is 90 mmHg or higher if they are not taking antihypertensive medication. The average of two or more readings obtained at each of two or more visits following an initial blood pressure screening serves as the basis for this definition.

4. **Blood Pressure Control:** Adult blood pressure is considered normal when it is 120 mm Hg during the heart's systolic beat and 80 mm Hg during the heart's diastolic beat. Readings are maintained in a prolonged period as HTN cannot be diagnosed from a single BP Measurement. No readings above SBP 140mmHG and DBP 90mmHg.

Research Hypotheses

1. $H_0: \mu_A = \mu_B$

There is no significant increase in blood pressure control among adults with hypertension in the pedometer-based physical activity program as compared to those who were not.

$H_1: \mu_A \neq \mu_B$

There is a significant increase in blood pressure control among adults with hypertension in the pedometer-based physical activity program as compared to those who were not.

2. $H_0: \mu_A = \mu_B$

There is no significant increase in health-promoting behavior (self-regulation) among adults with hypertension who used wearable technology (pedometer) as compared to those who did not.

$H_1: \mu_A \neq \mu_B$

There is a significant increase in health-promoting behavior (self-regulation) among adults with hypertension who used wearable technology (pedometer) as compared to those who did not.

Chapter III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Information about the study technique is included in this chapter. The study design, the intervention, the sample and sampling methods, the research environment, the research tool, the methods for collecting data, ethical issues, and the schedule for data management and analysis are all included in this chapter. The purpose of the study is to assess how well an exercise program based on pedometers lowers blood pressure in people receiving treatment at a tertiary hospital in Quezon City, the Philippines.

COVID-19 has changed people's lives globally. The COVID-19 pandemic greatly affected human lives - physically, psychologically, and socio-economically. Several nations have imposed stringent physical-social separation measures in an effort to stop the virus's transmission and safeguard the most susceptible populations (Armitage and Nellums, 2020).

The epidemic had an impact on research study conduct as well. As the number of COVID-19 cases continues to rise and various community quarantine levels and limits are put in place, it is critical to make sure that all participants are safe and healthy. This is especially crucial since research participants have hypertension and are more likely to experience COVID-19 problems. It is deemed necessary to utilize hybrid and innovative ways on how to sustain the research process, especially the data collection procedure. As part of social distancing tactics, health care institutions have moved away from in-person elective patient treatment, including regular outpatient clinics, and toward telemedicine/teleconsultation. (Nadar et.al., 2020).

Research Design

The study used a one-group before-after quasi-experimental design in which blood pressure, the dependent variable, was assessed both before and after the intervention (posttest and pretest). The same measures are employed in the pretest and posttest, and variations in the dependent variable between the two are considered to represent the adjustments made by the intervention (pedometer-based physical activity program). This study aims to know how walking in escalation per step in each day as physical activity and reaching 10,000 steps per day relates to adult hypertensive blood pressure control.

Complete experimental control is not achievable in a quasi-experimental approach. Research designs known as quasi-experiments are those in which the investigator starts a therapy or intervention but where some elements of a genuine experiment are absent. Because of the characteristics of the available individuals or the independent variable, control could not be feasible. A quasi-experimental design usually lacks the element of randomization. This design allows the researcher to examine variables to ascertain if a cause-effect relationship exists. (White & Sabarwal, 2014).

Research Setting

The study was conducted at the Philippine Heart Center, East Avenue, Quezon City, Philippines. This is a level 4 tertiary government-owned and controlled corporation (GOCC) specialty hospital with a 478-bed capacity accredited by the Department of Health and other regulatory agencies.

Study Population and Sampling Technique

Participants included in the study met the following inclusion criteria: (1) Outpatients at the Philippine Heart Center, (2) diagnosed with hypertension, (3) on hypertension

monotherapy, (4) 21 to 65 years old, (5) computer literate or has the ability to participate in an online physical activity intervention, and (5) with a mobile device and internet connection. Physical activity of adults with hypertension is matched by age, sex, ejection fraction, and the Canadian Classification System.

Severe lung illnesses, neurocognitive abnormalities, and physical restrictions that would prohibit individuals from engaging in the pedometer-based physical activity program were among the exclusion criteria. Additionally, participants who were unable to provide appropriate answers to questions on their psychological and health-related quality of life would be disqualified. Other hypertensive adults were excluded from the study if they belong to CCS III-IV, and with any of the following comorbidities: cerebrovascular accident, congestive heart failure, hemodynamically significant valve problems, end-stage organ disease, malignancies, congenital heart disease, psychiatric illness, chronic infectious problems, and chronic debilitating illness which will prevent them from doing the exercise program. Additionally, target participants who were unable to navigate through the different online platforms and do not have a mobile device or internet access will be excluded in this study.

There was an investigation of G*power. The t-test, which measures the difference between two dependent (paired) means, was used to do the a priori power analysis. With an alpha of 0.05, power of 0.80, and effect size (Cohen's *d*) of 0.50, the analysis was configured for two tails. According to Cohen (1988), a power of 0.80 or higher is acceptable, and a Cohen's *d* of 0.5 is considered a medium effect size. Thus, the researcher based the analysis parameters on these conventions. The calculated total sample size needed is 34 subjects (*see Figure 5*).

Convenience sampling was used in this study. This sampling design entails using the most conveniently available people as participants (Polit & Beck, 2008).

Figure 5. Calculated sample size using G*power software.

A letter of intent to conduct research (see Appendix B) was presented to the Philippine Heart Center, East Avenue, Quezon City, Philippines. The letter was sent to the following departments for courtesy and approval: Department of Research and Training, Institutional Ethics Review Board, Adult Cardiology Department, Employee Health Clinic, Division of Nursing Services, and Data IT Services with the continued guidance of the University of the Philippines Open University adviser, Professor Rita C. Ramos RN, MAN, and co-researcher/s, Dr Adrian Patrick Calimag and Ms. Edreck EstiokoRN, MAN. Full approval from the IERB is sought prior to the start of the study's data collection procedure.

A master list of adults diagnosed with hypertension coming from the employee registry was extracted using the facility's electronic medical system (Medtrak). The list was requested from the IT Department of the facility having the following information (see

Appendix C): Name, Age, Sex, Mobile number, email address, current blood pressure, and recorded height/weight (if available). Following the acquisition of the master list, a recruitment letter (*see Appendix D*) and an informed consent form (*see separate ICF form*) was sent via email to the adult employees potentially eligible for the study. The recruitment letter provided an explanation of the study including the overview, its objectives, duration of the study, what is expected of the participants, the study procedure, and the rights of the participants including the risks and benefits.

Participants was enrolled upon voluntary consent to participate in the study. Specific details in obtaining informed consent from participants was discussed under Section H.

A PAR-Q initial screening test was conducted by the Cardiology Fellow. After passing the PAR-Q Test, the participant was required to undergo a physical check up with the Employee Health Clinic Physician to ascertain physical fitness prior to the walking steps intervention.

Study Instruments

The research's description, its goal, and a declaration guaranteeing the confidentiality of all data collected for the study were all included on the first page of the participant information sheet. The PHC ERB Chairman, Research Assistants, Research Advisor, Co-Researcher(s) (Nurse and Cardiology Fellow), and Researcher's contact information is given.

The link to the online participant packet was given to each participant. The link included the Google Forms: 1) PAR-Q rendered screening Questionnaire by the Cardiology Fellow (co-researcher) 2) ISR 3) Pedometer Walking Step Counts Log Sheet 4) Blood Pressure Log Sheet and 5) Demographics and anthropometric measurements such as height in cm,

weight in kgs, body mass index (BMI), Heart Rate and average recorded blood pressure in mmHg for the last three health visits.

The RA initiated an interview-administered completion of the above-mentioned forms (in exception of the PAR-Q test) via a phone call. The questionnaire has three parts: (a) demographics and anthropometric measurement; (b) Index of Self-Regulation (ISR); and (c) Pre-Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PAR-Q+). Anthropometric measurements, baseline vital signs, and sociodemographic information were gathered in the first section. The subjects self-reported their height (meters) and body weight (kilograms). Body weight divided by squared height (kg/m^2) will get BMI. The degree of self-regulation for physical activity among the participants was assessed using the second section of the questionnaire. The Fleury (1998) Index of Self-Regulation (ISR) Scale was used to evaluate self-regulation both before and after the intervention. Nine Likert-scale items, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree), made up the ISR. The tool's dependability is comparatively strong, with a Cronbach's α of 0.885. The ISR should take five to ten minutes to complete. Higher levels of self-regulation for physical activity were indicated by higher total scores. The research assistant responded to any queries or concerns from the participants.

The Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire for Everyone (PAR-Q+) screening test that lasted for approximately 10 minutes was conducted by the Cardiology fellow. The test was done after the RA completed the rest of the mentioned questionnaire forms. PAR-Q+ signals the readiness of the participants in the walking activity (see *Appendix G*). This instrument demonstrated moderate-to-high validity against subjective measures of physical activity and low-to-moderate validity ($r_w = 0.13$ to 0.48) against measures of objectively measured physical activity. This is a tool that seeks further advice from a medical doctor or a qualified exercise professional before becoming more physically active.

Intervention

The benchmark for measuring physical activity was 10,000 walking steps per day on average, with moderate (METs = 2–5) and high (METs > 5) intensities. Using a pedometer (Brand: Steps count SC-01, Deep River, Ontario, Canada), objective walking behavior was evaluated.

A cut-off of 7,000 or more steps per day during an average 3-day period was required to determine if participants were fulfilling criteria based on pedometer steps. A 30-day walking program should be pursued if one reaches a cut-off point of 7,000 steps per day during an average 3-day period. The major tactic in this intervention was goal formulation using stages. Individual goals were mostly focused on engaging in activities that gradually increase step count over time, contingent on mobility level and recognized lifestyle characteristics. Specific activities included walking rather than driving to the shopping center or marketplace if accessible and with consideration of the community quarantine restrictions implemented in the region. Walking to a friend's house rather than using the telephone.

The researcher kept in touch with the participants in a one-on-one meeting at a pre-arranged time each week to discuss progress and new daily step targets for the subsequent week. Facebook Messenger was used during these virtual meetings as this is more accessible to the participants.

Specifically, the pedometer-based physical activity program consisted of walking steps, self-driven monitoring, and a health teaching activity.

1. Pedometers

Researchers and practitioners frequently employ pedometers, which are straightforward, low-cost body-worn motion sensors, to evaluate walking and other

ambulatory activities as well as physical activity habits. To direct their efforts, physical activity indices calculated by pedometers are required. In particular, a pedometer assesses steps/day recommendations and tries to convert current physical activity standards into steps/day equivalents.

Pedometers were continuously attached to participants for a thirty (30)-day period. The use of a pedometer as an interventional tool is an attempt to mobilize physical activity in adults with hypertension. The pedometer displays a number of steps while looking forward to 10,000 steps daily. With an average stride length of 2.1 to 2.5 feet, a mile may be covered in more than 2,000 steps, and a mile can be nearly covered in 10,000 steps.

The participants received a Formvan LCD Run Step Pedometer Walking Distance Calorie Counter. The internal mechanism of this pedometer type is identical to that of the Yamax SW series pedometer, which is frequently employed in research involving the tracking of physical activity. With each step, a horizontal lever arm supported by a spring opens and closes an electric circuit that counts the number of steps. Moreover, it has three modes which measure the number of steps taken, distance covered (in kilometers) and calories burned. It calculates steps based on movement, estimates distance traveled, and estimates the calories consumed. Additionally, it has a feature for alerts or reminders in times of extended sedentary time. The participant can view a real-time number of steps.

The pedometer was distributed by the nurse facilitator with complete device instruction and a return demonstration prior to use. The morning after getting the pedometer, participants began recording their daily steps for a period of seven days. The participant wore it for seven days in a row. Participants used their pedometer upon waking up in the morning to monitor steps taken throughout the day and remove them prior to sleeping at

night. They recorded their daily number of steps at the end of the day before going to sleep using the monitoring tool through Google Forms (*see Appendix H*).

The research assistant (RA) sent daily text messages to the participants to start wearing their pedometers in the morning and to remove the pedometers at night and to record achieved walking steps daily. Likewise, the RA sent a weekly (Friday) text message to participants to go to Employee Clinic for BP Measurement and record it in the BP Log Sheet. Throughout the 30-day intervention period, the participants were informed to seek immediate consultation from the Cardiology fellow for any signs or symptoms felt that are presumed or possibly induced by the walking steps. The nurse facilitator monitored and encouraged participants to always wear their pedometer, motivated them a target of 10,000 walking steps, instructed them to go to the employee clinic every Friday to check and record their BP, and monitored for any untoward signs and symptoms that are presumed or is possibly induced by the walking steps as a physical activity.

2. Health Teaching

A short video presentation on hypertension prevention through lifestyle modification was presented to the participants prior to the intervention phase. The said link comes with the initial packet uploaded on their email. This aims to further educate the participants on lifestyle modification to prevent hypertension (conservative management), the role of regular physical activity on blood pressure control, as well as the use of pedometers. Furthermore, a pamphlet published by DOH Philippines containing information on hypertension, signs and symptoms, management, and possible complications if left untreated was given to the participants. The research assistant answered questions or clarifications on hypertension prevention through lifestyle modification as a part of the health teaching.

Engaging in regular physical exercise for at least 20 minutes, three to four times a week, or 10,000 steps a day, is part of the therapy of hypertension. The participants were received a supplementary brochure with basic physical exercises they may do at home or at work.

Data Collection

Baseline (Pre-Intervention) Measurements

A recruitment letter and Participation to Research (Consent) was disseminated via email. Voluntary consent will be signed prior to Screening and data collection. The RA initiated the completion of the following questionnaire in Google Forms. Phone interviews were scheduled to answer the following information: 1) Socio-demographics and anthropometric measurements such as height (in cm), weight (in kg), BMI, heart rate, and averaged recorded blood pressure (for the last three employee health visits); 2) index of self-regulation (ISR); and 3) health teaching through a video presentation. The health teaching included the following topics: a) hypertension prevention through lifestyle modification; b) importance of physical activity; and c) physical exercise/s.

The Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire for Everyone (PAR-Q+) screening test lasting for approximately 10 minutes was conducted by the Cardiology fellow in an informed location. If the participant passed the PAR-Q+ screening test, a physical checkup was scheduled at the employee health clinic. The participant should pass the physical checkup and clearance from the employee health MD to start the intervention.

Outcome (During and Post-Intervention) Measurements

A pedometer was needed for the intervention in order to track the number of walking steps. The nurse facilitator gave out the pedometer. She gave instructions in writing and demonstrated how to use the pedometer correctly in return. The participants were

consistently reminded to wear the pedometer, log their steps at the end of the day, and have their blood pressure measured and documented at the employee health clinic once a week (every Friday). The intervention lasted for 30 days. Pedometers were kept by the participants after the intervention period.

The nurse facilitator and Cardiology fellow continuously observed the participants during the intervention to oversee their safety while at work. They acted as first responders for the participants if there were any medical concerns that arose. The employee health nurse took the participants BP using the Digital Omron BP Apparatus since this was the available device used in the clinic and the participants also recorded their BP on the BP log sheet.

Sphygmomanometers come in three varieties. Because digital sphygmomanometers are automated, blood pressure readings may be obtained without the requirement for a person to hold the cuff or hear the Korotkoff noises. The components of a manual sphygmomanometer are a mercury column and aneroid dial. With the exception of periodic calibration for aneroid devices, these mercury and aneroid devices operate quite similarly. BP readings were recorded using the Google forms log sheet.

At the end of the intervention, the Cardiology fellow re-evaluated the medical status of participants to ensure whether the intervention caused any disease, disability, or adverse events among the participants. A post-test for ISR Scale was administered through Google Forms assisted by the RA, for the purpose of comparison with the pre-intervention scores. The figure below shows the flowchart of the data collection.

Figure 6. Flowchart of Data Collection

Data Encoding and Analysis

The researcher extracted the data collected from the Google Forms as Microsoft Excel file format. Data included the sociodemographic and anthropometric measurements, PAR-Q, ISR and BP/walking steps log sheets; and was statistically analyzed using SPSS Statistics. The researcher performed a statistical analysis of the data. The subjects' sociodemographic and clinical features were described using descriptive statistics. To better present the facts, tables and graphs were used.

The study conducted as presented below where O1 stands for the baseline blood pressure of participants; X means intervention and O2 stands for the one (1) month BP Control outcome in 30-days.

$$O_1---X---O_2$$

There are two (2) main variables identified in the study. The pedometer-based Physical Activity (Walking) as an interventional program is the study's independent variable. The dependent variable results in an outcome on blood pressure control measured on a weekly basis within a 30-day duration.

The study included participants undergoing a one month of walking intervention, achieving 7,000 minimum steps to 10,000 steps daily for a 30-day period. Blood pressure was taken and logged during the weekly visit at the Employee Health Clinic.

Table 3

Coding Scheme of Research Variables

Variables	Category	Code
Age	21-39 years	1
	40-50 years	2
	50-60 years	3
	> 65 years	4
Sex	Male	1
	Female	2

A two-tailed dependent/paired t-test was used to determine the effectiveness of the pedometer-based physical activity package on pre- and post-intervention blood pressure.

Likewise, a paired t-test was also used to determine the relationship between the use of wearable technology (pedometer) and health-promoting behavior (self-regulation) among adults with hypertension. A p-value of <0.05 is considered significant. Table 4 shows the statistical tests to be used for each of the specific objectives.

Table 4

Statistical Analysis Plan

Objectives	Variables	Level of Measurement	Statistical Test
1 Describe the demographic and clinical characteristics of adults with hypertension.	a. Age b. Sex c. Blood Pressure d. Heart Rate e. Body Mass Index (BMI) f. Comorbidities/ Risk Factors	Ratio Nominal Ordinal Ratio Ratio Nominal	Descriptive Statistics (frequency, percentage, measures of central tendency)
2 Determine the association between a pedometer-based physical activity program and blood pressure control.	Pedometer-based physical activity program, and: a. Systolic blood pressure (pre- and post-intervention) b. Diastolic blood pressure (pre- and post-intervention)	Nominal Ratio Ratio	Two-tailed dependent/paired t-test
3 Determine the association between the use of wearable technology for blood pressure control (pedometer) and health-promoting behavior (self-regulation) among adults with hypertension.	Pedometer-based physical activity program, and: a. Self-regulation Scores (pre- and post-intervention)	Nominal Interval	Two-tailed dependent/paired t-test

Ethical Considerations

The World Medical Association's (2013) Declaration of Helsinki, the Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences' (2016) WHO International Ethical Guidelines for Health-related Research Involving Humans, and the Philippine Health Research Ethics Board's (2017) National Ethical Guidelines for Health and Health-Related Research all served as the foundation for the conduct of this study. The researcher followed the guidelines and recommendations of the Philippine Heart Center Institutional Ethics Review Board (PHC IERB) to get informed consent and review and approval of the study protocol before beginning the investigation.

1. Social Value

This study will provide Philippine data on the effectiveness of a pedometer- based physical activity program on blood pressure control of adults with hypertension. Knowledge gained from this study will empower nursing and medical practitioners in creating treatment plans and improving health education towards hypertension prevention, maintenance, and recovery. The PHC's Preventive Cardiology Department may be able to create an employee hypertension group which aims at the continuous hypertension control through lifestyle modification interventions, including a pedometer-based physical activity program which will also increase the quality of life as well as productivity in the work setting.

2. Informed Consent

The RA facilitated the gathering of informed consent and conduct of data collection and collation. Participants were contacted through email and telephone call as provided. Informed consent was secured from the participants at the time of recruitment for the study. Details regarding their participation were discussed without deception, coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Information about the study was also explained to the

participants by the research assistant, in a language and manner that is suitable to their capacity and level of understanding. The study's participants were made aware that their participation was entirely voluntary and that they may end it at any point. The consent form indicated the extent and duration of participation that they would have for the study.

The outline of the informed consent was adapted from the ICF template of the Philippine Heart Center - Institutional Ethics Review Board.

The research team applied the four main ethical principles of autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice when caring for adult hospital employees.

3. Vulnerability

There were no vulnerable population groups involved in the study.

4. Risks, Benefits, and Safety

This study involved minimal risk. Caring for hypertensive adults can pose a unique set of practical challenges and ethical dilemmas. Risks may include, but are not limited to, discomfort (having to wear a pedometer), inconvenience, loss of time and risk to data privacy. The researcher and the RA had open communication lines during the study to address immediate concerns of the participants. The phone numbers and email addresses of the researcher, RA, Cardiology fellow and the nurse facilitator were given to the participants as well.

The researcher scheduled weekly follow-up to the participants via Facebook Messenger to evaluate steps progress, reminding them to monitor log in sheets for walking steps and BP recording, reiterating hypertension health teachings on lifestyle modification and answer questions or any clarifications with regards to the research. The nurse facilitator

and Cardiology fellow were the go-to persons in the presence of any untoward medical signs and symptoms felt during the intervention phase.

Participants benefited from the study by being able to monitor and assess their daily steps in relation to their physical activity. They also received a brief health teaching on the management of hypertension, blood pressure control, and physical activity prior to the intervention.

In the future, the results of the study may be able to contribute to health promotion and in developing a cost-effective physical activity program geared toward hypertension prevention and management, maintenance, and recovery.

5. Privacy and Confidentiality

This study was compliant with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly ensured throughout the conduct of the study. A code assigned to each participant was used in the Google Forms questionnaire, which was only known to the Researcher. Furthermore, associated codes and contact details of the participants were maintained in a master list available only to the researcher and the research assistants. The names of the participants were not divulged upon the reporting of results or the publication of the research study.

The participants were informed through the informed consent form about the measures that were undertaken to maintain their privacy and confidentiality, and that the Ethics Review Board or other regulatory authorities might also have access to the information but only for verification of data and procedures.

Assurance of the anonymity of data was committed; the data gathered through Google Forms were not used indiscreetly nor their names reported. Access to the data provided by

the participants were only accessed by the researcher. The cloud copy of data will be deleted after copying the data set on the computer. The researcher valued diversity, promoted beneficence, and prevented harm to all participants. With the use of online platforms in the conduct of this study, the researcher upheld utmost data security as stated in the Data Privacy Statement of these platforms: <https://bit.ly/GooglePrivacyLink>/<https://bit.ly/FacebookPrivacyLink>. For the virtual meeting, the link was password-protected and was only provided to the participants.

6. Transparency

The researcher maintained full disclosure of any aspects of the study that would affect the participants' safety or rights, or that might have an influence on their ability to give informed consent. Additionally, all researchers are GCP-trained. The researcher declared no conflict of interest in the study.

COVID-19 Considerations

In light of the COVID-19 pandemic in the country, recruitment and data collection made use of online platforms: a virtual approach using telephone/mobile phone interviews, e-mails for instructions, questionnaires and log sheets using Google forms and virtual meetings using Facebook video chat.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter presents, analyses, and interprets the findings of the study according to the specific objectives. Data analysis was conducted and revealed the following results. The patients' clinical and demographic features were compiled using descriptive statistics. For categorical variables, frequency and percentage were utilized, and for continuously distributed normally distributed variables, mean and SD. ANOVA was employed to ascertain the variation in a patient's observed blood pressure between the pre- and post-test periods.

Socio-demographic profile

There were a total of 39 participants who agreed to join in the study. The participants who joined the intervention signed the informed consent form prior to the activities and willingly participated in the study. Table 5 below shows their demographic profile.

Table 5

Demographic Profile of the Participants

Variables	Frequency (Percentage)	Cumulative Percentage
Age (years) (<i>M=</i>, <i>SD=</i>)		
Sex		
Female	18 (80%)	80.00%
Male	21 (20.00%)	100.0%
ACS	0(0)	0
Diabetes Mellitus	15 (38.5%)	38.5%
Smoking	21 (53.8%)	53.8%
Dyslipidemia	14 (35.9%)	35.9%
Cerebrovascular Accident	0(0)	0
Obesity	0 (0)	0

Age. Results showed that the majority of the participants are adults. Over 60% of older persons in the National Health and Nutrition Survey reported having a diagnosis of hypertension, indicating that age is a known risk factor for the development of hypertension.

Gender. Most of the participants are male (N=21) while there are also females (N=18). In the study of Zhang & Moran (2017), it is discovered that women are diagnosed with hypertension more frequently, and a major contributing cause to this is a greater incidence of healthcare consumption. However, men and higher socioeconomic groups had higher levels of physical activity; racial, genetic, interpersonal, and environmental variables all influence physical activity behavior throughout the course of a person's lifetime (Hayes et al., 2022).

For the **known medical conditions of the respondents**, most of them have smoking history (N=21), 15 of them have diabetes mellitus and 14 have dyslipidemia. Some risk factors for hypertension cannot be changed, such as having a family history of the condition, being older than 65, and having co-occurring conditions like diabetes and kidney disease. However, some risk factors can be changed, such as using tobacco products and alcohol, eating a high-fat diet, taking excessive amounts of salt, being inactive, and being obese (WHO 2019). These lifestyle-related modifiable risk factors for hypertension.

Table 6

Descriptive statistics for Variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	55.05	6.613
SBP	122.82	7.930
DBP	82.56	7.511
HR	78.33	7.013
Height	162.49	6.672
Weight	66.56	6.269
BMI	25.2559	1.87218

Table 6 above presents the descriptive statistics of the variables: age, Systolic Blood Pressure, Diastolic Blood Pressure, Heart Rate, Height, Weight, and Body Mass Index (BMI) of the participants before the intervention. It is necessary to determine the baseline data of the participants to be able to have a comparison after the intervention. In terms of age there is a $M=55.05$; $SD=6.613$, on average, systolic BP (SBP) rises throughout life in most individuals and finally reaches a plateau in late life (Zhou et al., 2019). But blood pressure trajectories can fluctuate with age and are probably associated with varying degrees of cardiovascular risk. Previous research has looked at the age at which a disease first manifests and how that affects unfavorable consequences when it comes to chronic conditions like diabetes and obesity (Suvila et al., 2020).

Index of Self-regulation

Pedometers are contemporary devices that serve as both an activity tracker and a motivator by tracking a person's daily ambulatory activity. 10,000 steps a day is a globally recognized objective. Pedometer-based workplace physical activity interventions are more successful than those without them, according to a 2013 systematic review (Chen & Magnussen, 2013). Table 7 below shows the responses of the participants on the index of self-regulation.

Table 7

Frequency and Percentage of Participants' Responses in Index of Self-regulation

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
	Frequency (%)					
1. <i>Iniisip ko ang mga pakinabang ng regular na pisikal na aktibidad</i>	4 (10.26)	11 (28.21)	12 (30.77)	12 (30.77)	0	0
2. <i>Pinapaalala ko sa sarili ko ang mabuting ginagawa ko sa pamamagitan ng</i>	0	11 (28.21)	10 (25.64)	18 (46.15)	0	0

<i>pananatiling aktibo sa pisikal</i>						
3. <i>Pinapaalala ko sa aking sarili ang kahalagahan ng pisikal na aktibidad</i>	2 (5.13)	5 (12.82)	13 (33.33)	19 (48.72)	0	0
4. <i>Sinusubaybayan ko ang mga paraan kung paano ako mananatiling aktibo sa pisikal</i>	0	10 (25.64)	12 (30.77)	17 (43.59)	0	0
5. <i>Tinitingnan ko ang mga palatandaan ng pagiging aktibo pampisikal.</i>	6 (15.38)	12 (30.77)	17 (43.59)	4 (10.26)	0	0
6. <i>Sinusubaybayan ko ang aking sarili upang makita kung natutugunan ko ang aking mga layunin para sa pisikal na aktibidad</i>	3 (7.69)	11 (28.21)	22 (56.41)	3 (7.69)	0	0
7. <i>Natutunan ko ang mga bagong gawi na makakatulong sa akin na makilahok sa pisikal na aktibidad</i>	1 (2.56)	7 (17.95)	11 (28.21)	20 (51.28)	0	0
8. <i>Natutunan ko ang mga bagong paraan upang manatiling aktibong pisikal.</i>	3 (7.69)	9 (23.08)	14 (35.9)	13 (33.33)	0	0
9. <i>Natutunan kong gumawa ng mga pagbabago sa aking pisikal na aktibidad na maaari kong ikabuhay.</i>	3 (7.69)	10 (25.64)	12 (30.77)	14 (35.9)	0	0

Self-regulation is the process by which people take ownership of their education by keeping an eye on their own development and use techniques to pursue their own objectives. Self-regulated learners—those who exhibit self-directed behavior—think that they have a significant influence on their success and ability to accomplish their objectives. During the first stages of self-regulated learning, people become more aware of themselves by self-observing (self-monitoring, self-recording), which starts the goal-setting process. According to Petlichkoff (2004), these techniques assist people in assessing their existing behavior—that is, their level of physical activity—so they may establish objectives for personal growth. (e.g., raise step counts).

Self-reporting, usually with a pedometer, has benefits for the individual since it gives them a sense of accountability and self-efficacy. In general, basic pedometers have demonstrated satisfactory validity and low error rates when it comes to counting daily steps (Park et al., 2014). In another study it is reported that pedometer usage demonstrated the cardiac patients' motivation to move. The patients felt driven to walk, even if not all components of motivation were autonomous and self-determined. Each patient was able to select the type of exercise they wished to engage in and make continuing modifications to their walking regimen thanks to the clear steps and constant monitoring of their own walking activity. Walking motivation came from the quick input on step activity and the anticipated health advantages. Ultimately, the ability to monitor patients while walking using a pedometer allowed them to feel cared for and supported (Thorup, 2016). The results of this study showed that the pedometer provided independence from therapy that was standardized. Step targets became pliable, and the pedometer offered chances to customize tasks in relation to day-to-day life. This led to an increased independence and autonomy.

Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire for Everyone

An individual's risk of developing hypertension and declining physical activity levels increases with age. The understanding of how exercise lowers blood pressure and the clinically significant ambulatory blood pressure has improved due to scientific advancements, however this is not represented in the hypertension recommendations for clinical management of hypertension (Hayes et al., 2022).

Many chronic illnesses, including diabetes, obesity, cancer, depression, hypertension, and cardiovascular disease, can be avoided by regular physical exercise. It has been shown that physical inactivity ranks as the fourth most important risk factor for mortality worldwide, accounting for an estimated 3.2 million deaths annually (WHO, 2017).

There has been variability in the outcomes of earlier research on the impact of walking treatments on blood pressure. In order to manage blood pressure, a meta-analysis of walking programs found beneficial effects from a variety of study designs (Kelley, 2001); restricted to a particular population, such as adults who are not active or who have type 2 diabetes (Oja, 2018); complex interventions, like combining walking, jogging, and/or running (Shabaaninia, 2017); or compared a walking intervention with participants in the control group who also received an intervention, like an active pedometer-based walking intervention (Vetrovsky, 2018) or lifestyle modification, like health education (Zhang, 2012).

Blood Pressure Monitoring

Technology is creating a wide scope of research in this field; home BP monitoring using technological tools is one of the effective ways of reducing blood pressure. Table 4 below presents the blood pressure monitoring of the participants in terms of mean and standard deviation. There is a close mean between the baseline data ($M=122.82$) and week 1 data ($M=122.31$) of SBP and DBP ($M=82.56$; $M=82.05$).

Table 8

Blood pressure monitoring (n=39)

	Systolic blood pressure		Diastolic blood pressure	
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation
Baseline	122.82	7.93	82.56	7.51
Week 1	122.31	8.42	82.05	7.32
Week 2	120.51	8.57	79.49	6.05
Week 3	115.38	8.84	79.23	6.23
Week 4	113.85	8.47	78.46	5.40
P-value	<0.001		<0.001	

It can also be seen from the table above that as the intervention is continuously done every week, the mean and standard deviation is also decreasing. For week 3 SBP

($M=115.38$; $SD=8.84$), week 3 DBP ($M=79.23$; $SD=6.23$). For week 4 SBP ($M=113.85$; $SD=8.47$) and week 4 DBP ($M=78.46$; $SD=5.40$). One typical physical activity that is necessary for independence in carrying out everyday tasks is walking. Steps taken per day and the amount of time spent on them have been proposed as measures of functional capacity (Chen et al., 2022). Pedometers are user-friendly devices that offer users feedback on their daily activity. Research findings indicate that pedometers can be a useful instrument for tracking and promoting physical activity in individuals in good health (Chen et al., 2022).

Association of Wearable Technology and Self-Regulation

Users of wearable technology devices may get real-time data on health-related elements including heart rate, step counts, and physical activity. People may be inspired to lead healthier and more active lifestyles by using wearable technology to measure physical activity levels and raise awareness (Donnachie et al., 2017). Wearable technology may help people enhance their health, but the study has produced contradictory findings.

Table 9

Pairwise Comparison of Systolic Blood Pressure from Week 1 to Week 4

(I) factor1	(J) factor1	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig. ^a
Week 1	Week 2	2.821	.086
	Week 3	7.436	.000
	Week 4	8.974	.000
Week 2	Week 1	-2.821	.086
	Week 3	4.615	.000
	Week 4	6.154	.000
Week 3	Week 1	-7.436	.000
	Week 2	-4.615	.000
	Week 4	1.538	.074
Week 4	Week 1	-8.974	.000
	Week 2	-6.154	.000
	Week 3	-1.538	.074

Week 1 has a significant difference to Week 3 and Week 4. In the study of Lee et al (2021), they came to the conclusion that there is moderate-to-strong evidence that walking
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lowers blood pressure. The purpose of their study is to ascertain how walking affects blood pressure in relation to physical activity interventions. Week 2 has significant difference to Week 3 and Week 4. Week 3 has significant difference to Week 1 and Week 2. Week 4 has a significant difference to Week 1 and Week 2.

People with cardiometabolic disorders may be able to enhance their levels of physical activity and health-related habits with the help of wearable activity monitors. Recently, wearable activity trackers have gained popularity as a way to monitor physical activity levels and encourage individuals with various chronic conditions, such as cardiometabolic conditions (Afshin et al., 2016). The devices are easy to use, straightforward, reasonably priced, and have the potential to motivate users. In this study, individuals with hypertension who received therapies including the use of wearable activity trackers—particularly pedometers—showed higher levels of daily physical activity. Previous studies showed that when used in conjunction with programs that included routine visits with a health care provider, the use of pedometers was significantly associated with increased physical activity as compared to self-monitoring strategies that did not entail consultations (Hodkinson et al., 2021).

Table 10*Pairwise Comparison of Diastolic Blood Pressure from Week 1 to Week 4*

(I) factor1	(J) factor1	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig. ^b
Week 1	Week 2	.513	.960
	Week 3	3.077*	.001
	Week 4	3.333*	.001
Week 2	Week 1	-.513	.960
	Week 3	2.564*	.005
	Week 4	2.821*	.003
Week 3	Week 1	-3.077*	.001
	Week 2	-2.564*	.005
	Week 4	.256	1.000
Week 4	Week 1	-3.333*	.001
	Week 2	-2.821*	.003
	Week 3	-.256	1.000

In terms of the diastolic blood pressure, Weeks 1 and 2 of intervention has significant difference to Week 3 and Week 4, while Weeks 1 and 2 do not have significant difference from each other. This has the same results with the systolic blood pressure wherein BP becomes lower as the participants continuously do the walking intervention.

Previous research on the impact of walking treatments on blood pressure has yielded mixed results. A meta-analysis of walking programs for blood pressure management discovered beneficial effects from a variety of study designs (Kelley, 2001); restricted to a particular population, such as adults with type 2 diabetes (Cai, 2014) or those who are inactive (Oja, 2018); complex interventions, like combining walking, jogging, and/or running (Shabaaninia 2017); or compared a walking intervention with participants in the control group who also received an intervention, like an active walking intervention based on pedometers (Vetrovsky, 2018) or modified lifestyle choices, like health education (Zhang, 2012). It's also critical to look at underlying psychological processes that are recognized as important markers of long-term physical exercise commitment. This can improve understanding of possible barriers to long-term adherence and how to get around them. One

of the most important motivational theories that has been extensively studied in relation to physical exercise is the organismic integration theory, a subtheory of the self-determination theory (Ryan & Deci, 2017).

When combined, the study's findings might have a significant impact on how wearable technology encourages people to engage in physical activity. The study's main conclusions were that wearing wearable technology was linked to a gradual decrease in physical activity and that wearing wearable technology was linked to introjected motivation. Therefore, it's critical to take into account how people utilize wearable technology to encourage physical activity.

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

The primary goal of the research is to ascertain if a walking program based on pedometers is beneficial for controlling blood pressure in persons with hypertension who work in tertiary hospitals as a form of physical exercise. The study used a one-group before-after quasi-experimental design in which blood pressure, the dependent variable, was assessed both before and after the intervention (posttest and pretest). The same measures are employed in the pretest and posttest, and variations in the dependent variable between the two are understood as reflecting the modifications brought about by the intervention (a physical activity program based on pedometers). 39 people in all consented to participate in the research. Results showed that the majority of the participants are male adults. most of them have smoking history (N=21), 15 of them have diabetes mellitus and 14 have dyslipidemia. Study shows significant increase in blood pressure control among adults with Hypertension in the Pedometer-Based Physical Activity program as compared to those who were not.

Conclusion

The study's conclusions show that there is a substantial variation among the four locations. The two most prevalent causes of increased cardiovascular morbidity and death are physical inactivity and hypertension. Although there is growing evidence supporting the role of physical activity in managing hypertension and awareness of its devastating effects, it seems that guidelines undervalue the importance of physical activity and that clinicians underuse it as a primary and secondary preventive strategy.

For individuals with hypertension, a pedometer-based walking program that includes daily tracking is beneficial in encouraging walking and enhancing the favorable effects of blood pressure control. Determining the possible health advantages of walking is essential to the public health message since the reasons for these inconclusive outcomes are not evident.

Recommendation

Considering the foregoing findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher makes the following recommendations:

Adult Population: Adults must know that a sedentary lifestyle is costly and leads to co-morbid conditions. Strict adherence to regular physical activity and the use of a pedometer as a tool is essential in maintaining adequate physical activity.

Clinical Nursing Practice: Nurses can expand the application of nursing practice and better serve the sedentary population who may benefit from pedometer use. This will empower the future of nursing, facing the rapid influx of healthcare technology aimed at hastening community participation in the treatment regimen, lifestyle changes and wellness.

Medical/Nursing Administration: Ought to be abreast with current healthcare innovations such as the use of pedometer to engage patients to exercise thereby contributing to cardiovascular prevention and health promotion.

Allied Health Professionals: In order to increase patient safety, wearable technology is becoming more and more common in the medical field. The two main goals of this movement are to increase patient safety and reduce injuries to nurses and other medical professionals. Outcome of research mobilizes health care staff and personnel in joining the command for self-care, wellness and responsibility.

Nursing Research: In the light of the limitations identified and the findings of the study; it is recommended that a follow- up study using a larger sample size be undertaken for more reliable statistical results. Sound research that tells us what works on healthcare delivery, and with whom and where it works best, is of utmost benefit. In addition to comparing the impact of the walking program with and without the physical activity consultation, future phases of this project will look at adherence to the intervention and offer longitudinal data on health-related outcomes.

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- Effectiveness of a Pedometer-based Physical Activity Program...

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Appendices

Appendix A

Diagrammatic Workflow

Appendix B

Letter of Intent for the Conduct of Data Collection

TO:

THRU:

DATE: March ____, 2022

SUBJECT: Final Protocol #PHC.R.026.13 version 6.0

Warmest Greetings!

I am a continuing Master of Arts in Nursing Student at the University of the Philippines undergoing Thesis Course entitled:

“Effectiveness of a Pedometer-based Physical Activity Program on Blood Pressure Control among Adults with Hypertension in a Tertiary Hospital in Quezon City, Philippines”

I was a previous Staff Nurse at this Center in 1991 and was reinstated in 2016. I am currently working as a travel Cardio-Vascular nurse in the United States of America and I will be working with PHC CO-RN, Ms. Ma. Edreck Estioko and Cardiology Fellow, Dr. Aldrin Patrick Calimag as co-researchers. I will also be assisted by Ms. Amethyst Edreck Estioko (Research Assistant).

Upon IERB Approval, I humbly seek support from your department in conducting my data collection process.

My advisers are Dr. Araceli O. Balabagno, previous Dean of the UP College of Nursing and co-advised by Professor Rita C. Ramos, Program Chair of FMDS University of the Philippines Open University.

I am truly grateful for this opportunity. Hoping for your kindest consideration and generous support.

Respectfully yours,

MARY LORELEI MACAZO-CARAVEO

Master of Arts in Nursing
Major in Adult Health
Student
maryloirelei.caraveo@upou.edu.ph

Appendix C

Request Letter to PHC

PHILIPPINE HEART CENTER
East Avenue, Quezon City

L-ETR-CRD-CTR-2019-768

24 October 2019

MARY LORELEI MACAZO-CARAVEO
University of the Philippines Open University

Dear Ms. Caraveo:

Our office has received your research proposal last 21 October 2019 regarding your research proposal entitled **"The Effectiveness of a Pedometer-Based Walking Program on Blood Pressure Control among Adult Out-Patients with Primary Hypertension in a Tertiary Hospital in Quezon City, Philippines"**.

Attached please find pertinent requirements of the Division before we could process your request. This is from the Policy Manual of the Philippine Heart Center, Clinical Trial and Research Division under Clinical Research Department.

Thank you.

Truly yours,

ALEXANDER A. TUAZON, M.D.
Division Chief
Clinical Trial and Research Division

Noted by:

MARIA TERESA B. ABOLA, MD
Department Manager III
Clinical Research Department

By signing the conforme below, you hereby agree to abide with the conditions

CONFORME:

SIGNATURE OVER PRINTED NAME OF PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR
Date Signed: _____
AAT/MTBA/vmdtm

"A PHIC Accredited Health Care Provider"

Republic of the Philippines
PHILIPPINE HEART CENTER
East Avenue, Quezon City 1100, Philippines
Telephone No. 89252401 to 50 www.phc.gov.ph

APPROVAL NOTICE

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICS REVIEW BOARD

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MA. THERESA M. VILLANUEVA

LEAHDETTE O. PADUA, MD

Contact Person:

Noreen Malaca
Philippine Heart Center
8/F Medical Arts Building
East Avenue, Quezon City
Tel. no. 89252401 loc.3899
Email Add: irbphc@gmail.com

L-E-IRB-2023-153

Date: 11 April 2023

To: **Mary Lorelei Macazo-Caraveo, RN**
Philippine Heart Center
East Avenue, Quezon City 1100

IERB no.: PHC.IERB.06.21.102

Protocol No: PHC.R.026.13

Protocol Title: Effectiveness of a pedometer-based physical activity program on blood pressure control among adult out-patients with primary hypertension in a tertiary hospital in Quezon City, Philippines

Approval date : **11 April 2023**
Schedule of Continuing Review : **11 February 2024**
Expiration Date : **11 April 2024**

Thank you for your submission of documents for continuing review for the above mentioned study. The PHC-IERB has approved your submission. This approval is based on an appropriate risk/benefit ratio and a study design wherein the risks have been minimized. All researches/studies must be conducted in accordance with this approval submission.

It is the Principal Investigator's responsibility to obtain review and continued approval before the expiration date. You may not continue any research activity beyond the expiration date without IERB approval.

Failure to receive approval for continuing review before the expiration date will result in the automatic suspension of the approval of this protocol on the expiration date.

All changes or amendments to your protocol or consent form require review and approval by the IERB before implementation

If the research, including data analysis, has been completed or, if you wish to terminate the study, please notify the IERB.

If you have any question, please contact us at telephone no.89252401 loc.3899 or via email: irbphc@gmail.com. Please include your study title and IERB accession no. in all correspondence with this office.

RAFAEL R. TENORIO, MD
Chair, IERB

PHC.IERB.06.21.102

PHC.R.026.13

FM-E-IRB-2019-070
Rev. 05

PHILIPPINE HEART CENTER
East Avenue, Quezon City

RESEARCH PROPOSAL APPROVAL FORM

Study Number: OR.R.001.20

Date Submitted: 10 OCTOBER 2019

Title: "EFFECTIVENESS OF A Pedometer-based Physical Activity Program on Blood Pressure Control among Adult Out-patients with Primary Hypertension in a Tertiary Hospital in Quezon City, Philippines"

Principal Investigator: MARY LORELEI MACAZO-CARAVEO, RN

Technical Review:

MARIA NERISSA ATIENZA-DE LEON, M.D., M.M. *[Signature]* 9/29/2020 Approved Disapproved
Reviewer

RHALP JAYLORD L. VALENZUELA *[Signature]* 4/16/2021 Approved Disapproved
Reviewer

ALEXANDER A. TUAZON, M.D. Approved Disapproved
Reviewer

Comments:

Division Approval:

ALEXANDER A. TUAZON, M.D. *[Signature]* 4/20/21 Approved Disapproved
Division Chief
Clinical Trial and Research Division

Ethical Review:

RAFAEL R. TENORIO, M.D. *[Signature]* 20 April 2022 Approved Disapproved
Chairman, Institutional Ethics Review Board

Comments:

Department Approval:

MARIA TERESA B. ABOLA, M.D. *[Signature]* Approved Disapproved
Department Manager III
Clinical Research Department

FM-E-CRD-CTR-2019-002
Rev. 03

Appendix E

Master list of Hospital Employees with Hypertension

Participant Code	Name	Sex	Birthdate	Age	Occupation	City Address	Home/Mobile Phone Number	Email address
PHC-001								
PHC-002								
PHC-003								
PHC-004								
PHC-005								
PHC-006								
PHC-007								
PHC-008								
PHC-009								
PHC-010								
PHC-011								
PHC-012								
PHC-013								
PHC-014								
PHC-015								
PHC-016								
PHC-017								
PHC-018								
PHC-019								
PHC-020								
PHC-021								
PHC-022								

PHC-023								
PHC-024								

Appendix F

Recruitment Letter

Dear Mr/Ms _____,

Good day!

I am Mary Lorelei Macazo-Caraveo, a registered nurse currently taking up a Master of Arts in Nursing Major in Adult Health at the University of the Philippines. The increasing prevalence of hypertension among the adult population aged 20 and older in the country and the poor control of disease progression and emergence of various complications reflects the need to explore effective strategies to manage the risk factors of hypertension. One risk factor is physical inactivity. With modern innovations and technologies, wearable pedometers have been widely used to monitor fitness activity such as daily steps and calories burned. In this regard, I am conducting a study aimed at determining the *“Effectiveness of a Pedometer-based Physical Activity Program on Blood Pressure Control among Adults with Hypertension in a Tertiary Hospital in Quezon City, Philippines”*.

In line with this, I am inviting you to join the study since you qualify to the following criteria: (1) employed in Philippine Heart Center (2) diagnosed with hypertension, (3) on hypertension monotherapy, (4) 21 to 65 years old, (5) basic computer literacy (6) with mobile device and data or internet connection.

Participation in this study is voluntary and individual information/results will remain confidential. It will involve an interview process, Health-teaching modalities and Post-Evaluation Survey. You may decline to answer any of the questions if you wish. Further, you may decide to withdraw from this study at any time without any negative consequences by advising the Principal researcher.

If you have any questions regarding this study, or would like additional information to assist you in reaching a decision about participation, please contact the Researcher at phone number +15203365088 with email address maryloirelei.caraveo@upou.edu.ph /maryloirelei@yahoo.com or the Research Assistant, Amethyst Edreck Estioko at phone +63999-664-1350 and email address at amyjoyEdreckEstioko@gmail.com.

Looking forward to your favorable response.

Yours Sincerely,

Mary Lorelei Macazo-Caraveo
(Sample confirmation slip of continued participation)

Please fill out the following information below:
 Preferred method of contact:

Contact information:

(Mobile number)

(Email address)

Appendix G

Sociodemographic Data (Researcher-administered)

Google Forms link: <https://bit.ly/Sociodemographics>

Participant Identifier

CLINICAL DATA

Vital Signs

Blood Pressure _____

Heart Rate _____

Height (cm) _____

Weight (kg) _____

BMI _____

Date diagnosed with Hypertension (if known) _____

Known Medical Condition

<input type="checkbox"/>	Acute Coronary Syndrome / CAD
<input type="checkbox"/>	Diabetes Mellitus
<input type="checkbox"/>	Smoking

<input type="checkbox"/>	Dyslipidemia
<input type="checkbox"/>	Cerebrovascular Accident
<input type="checkbox"/>	Obesity
<input type="checkbox"/>	Others _____

Appendix H

Index of Self-Regulation Scale (Yeom & Fleury, 2011)

Google Forms link: <https://bit.ly/ISRScale>

Instruction: Please tick (✓) one box for each statement below to show how much you agree or disagree with it.

Panuto: Mangyaring Lagyan ng tsek (✓) ang isang kahon para sa bawat pahayag sa ibaba upang ipakita kung gaano ka sumasang-ayon o hindi sumasang-ayon dito.

	Strongly Agree (Lubos na hindi sumasang-ayon)	Disagree (Hindi sumasang-ayon)	Slightly Disagree (Hindi gaanong sumasang-ayon)	Slightly Agree (Bahagya ng sumasang-ayon)	Agree (Sumasang-ayon)	Strongly Agree (Lubos na sumasang-ayon)
1. Niisip ko ang... ...pakinabang... ...regular na... ...pisikal na... ...aktibidad						
2. Pinapaalala ko sa sarili ko ang mabuting ginagawa ko sa pamamagitan ng pananatiling aktibo sa pisikal						

3.Pinapaalala ko sa aking sarili ang kahalagahan ng pisikal na aktibidad						
4.Sinusubaybayan ko ang mga paraan kung paano ako mananatiling aktibo sa pisikal						
5.Tinitingnan ko ang mga palatandaan ng pagiging aktibo pampisikal.						
6.Sinusubaybayan ko ang aking sarili upang makita kung natutugunan ko ang aking mga layunin para sa pisikal na aktibidad						
7.Natutunan ko ang mga bagong gawina na makakatulong sa akin na makilahok sa pisikal na aktibidad						
8.Natutunan ko ang mga bagong paraan upang manatiling						

aktibong pisikal.						
9.Natutunan kong gumawa ng mga pagbabago sa aking pisikal na aktibidad na maaari kong ikabuhay.						

Appendix I

The Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire for Everyone (PAR-Q+)

Google Forms link: <https://bit.ly/PARQ2018>

SECTION 1: GENERAL HEALTH

Please read the 7 questions below carefully and answer each one honestly: check YES or NO.		YES	NO
1.	Has your doctor ever said that you have a heart condition OR high blood pressure?	χ	χ
2.	Do you feel pain in your chest at rest, during your daily activities of living, OR when you do physical activity?	χ	χ
3.	Do you lose balance because of dizziness OR have you lost consciousness in the last 12 months? Please answer NO if your dizziness was associated with over-breathing (including during vigorous exercise).	χ	χ
4.	Have you ever been diagnosed with another chronic medical condition (other than heart disease or high blood pressure)?	χ	χ
5.	Are you currently taking prescribed medications for a chronic medical condition?	χ	χ

6.	Do you have a bone or joint problem that could be made worse by becoming more physically active? Please answer NO if you had a joint problem in the past, but it does not limit your current ability to be physically active. For example, knee, ankle, shoulder or other.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7.	Has your doctor ever said that you should only do medically supervised physical activity?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If you answered YES to one or more of the questions above, please GO TO SECTION 2.

SECTION 2: CHRONIC MEDICAL CONDITIONS

Please read the questions below carefully and answer each one honestly: check YES or NO.		YES	NO
6.	Do you have a Respiratory Disease? This includes Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease, Asthma, Pulmonary High Blood Pressure	<input type="checkbox"/> If yes, answer questions 6a-6d	<input type="checkbox"/> If no, go to question 7
6a.	Do you have difficulty controlling your condition with medications or other physician-prescribed therapies? (Answer NO if you are not currently taking medications or other treatments)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6b.	Has your doctor ever said your blood oxygen level is low at rest or during exercise and/or that you require supplemental oxygen therapy?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	6c.	If asthmatic, do you currently have symptoms of chest tightness, wheezing, labored breathing, consistent cough (more than 2 days/week), or have you used your rescue medication more than twice in the last week?	χ	χ
	6d.	Has your doctor ever said you have high blood pressure in the blood vessels of your lungs?	χ	χ
7.	Do you have a Spinal Cord Injury? This includes Tetraplegia and Paraplegia		χ If yes, answer questions 7a-7c	χ If no, go to question 8
	7a.	Do you have difficulty controlling your condition with medications or other physician-prescribed therapies? (Answer NO if you are not currently taking medications or other treatments)	χ	χ
	7b.	Do you commonly exhibit low resting blood pressure significant enough to cause dizziness, lightheadedness, and/or fainting?	χ	χ
	7c.	Has your physician indicated that you exhibit sudden bouts of high blood pressure (known as Autonomic Dysreflexia)?	χ	χ
8.	Have you had a Stroke? This includes Transient Ischemic Attack (TIA) or Cerebrovascular Event		χ If yes, answer questions 8a-c	χ If no, go to question 9
	8a.	Do you have difficulty controlling your condition with medications or other physician-prescribed therapies? (Answer NO if you are not currently taking medications or other treatments)	χ	χ

	8b.	Do you have any impairment in walking or mobility?	χ	χ
	8c.	Have you experienced a stroke or impairment in nerves or muscles in the past 6 months?	χ	χ
9.	Do you have any other medical condition not listed above or do you live with two chronic conditions?		χ If yes, answer questions 9a-c	χ If no, read the advice on page 4
	9a.	Have you experienced a blackout, fainted, or lost consciousness as a result of a head injury within the last 12 months OR have you had a diagnosed concussion within the last 12 months?	χ	χ
	9b.	Do you have a medical condition that is not listed (such as epilepsy, neurological conditions, kidney problems)?	χ	χ
	9c.	Do you currently live with two chronic conditions?	χ	χ

If you answered NO to all of the follow-up questions about your medical condition, you are ready to become more physically active.

Appendix J

Daily Walking Steps Monitoring

Google Forms link: <https://bit.ly/DailyStepCount>

Participant Code:		
Date	Number of walking steps	Remarks

Day 1 (Baseline)	
Week 1	
Week 2	
Week 3	
Week 4	
30th day (Post)	
Code of Participant:	

Appendix L
Health Education Material

**ILANG PAYO PARA IWAS
ALTAPRESYON:**

- Kumain ng low-salt at low-fat diet
- Mag-ehersisyo nang 30 minuto kada araw
- Panatilihing tama ang timbang
- Iwasan ang pag-inom ng alak
- Ihinto ang paninigarilyo
- Bawasan ang stress sa tulong ng mga relaxation techniques tulad ng deep breathing at meditation
- Para sa karagdagang payo at kaalaman: Kumonsulta sa pinakamalapit na health center para sa karagdagang kaalaman

DOH OfficialDOHgov

Online Research Packet (containing the compiled Google Forms Link)

Online Research Packet

Effectiveness of a Pedometer-based Physical Activity Program on Blood Pressure Control among Adults with Hypertension in a Tertiary Hospital in Quezon City, Philippines

WELCOME!

The increasing prevalence of hypertension among the adult population aged 20 and older in the country and the poor control of disease progression and emergence of various complications reflects the need to explore effective strategies to manage the risk factors of hypertension. One risk factor is physical inactivity.

With modern innovations and technologies, wearable pedometers have been widely used to monitor fitness activity such as daily steps and calories burned.

The main purpose of the study is to determine the effectiveness of a pedometer-based walking program as a physical activity towards blood pressure control among adults with hypertension who are employed in a tertiary hospital

Researcher/s:

Mary Lorelei Caraveo, RN
Adrian Patrick Calimag, MD
Ma. Charisse Magallanes, RN, MAN

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0920-967-8368

Philippine Heart Center
8/F Medical and Arts Building
East Avenue, Quezon City, 1100 Philippines

GOOGLE FORMS LINKS

Survey/Questionnaire

Sociodemographic Data

<https://bit.ly/Sociodemographics>

Index of Self-Regulation Scale

<https://bit.ly/ISRScale>

Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire for Everyone (PAR-Q+)

<https://bit.ly/PARQ2018>

Online logsheets

Walking Steps²

<https://bit.ly/DailyStepCount>

Blood Pressure³

<https://bit.ly/BPmonitoring>

Notes:

1. Click on the link provided. You will be directed to the Google Forms link automatically. Take note of your participant code/identifier.
2. Walking steps are logged daily
3. Blood pressure measurement is done weekly (every Friday)

Researcher/s:

Mary Lorelei Caraveo, RN
Adrian Patrick Callimag, MD
Ma. Charisse Magallanes, RN, MAN

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0917-806-9943
0920-967-8368

Philippine Heart Center
8/F Medical and Arts Building
East Avenue, Quezon City, 1100 Philippines

PEDOMETER

HOW TO USE?

1. Reset the counter at the time you wake up.
2. Place it in your arm when you start your day.
3. Write the number of steps you had before you go to bed (You will also be reminded through SMS/text at 9:00 PM daily).
4. The pedometer will stay with you for 30 days.
5. It is not water-resistant and shockproof.
6. Do not shake unnecessarily as it records the metallic ball bouncing inside the pedometer.

ONLINE LOGSHEETS

WALKING STEPS

<https://bit.ly/DailyStepCount>

BLOOD PRESSURE

<https://bit.ly/BP monitoring>

NOTE:

1. Click on the link provided. You will be directed to the Google Forms link automatically. Take note of your participant code/identifier.
2. Walking steps are logged daily
3. Blood pressure measurement is done weekly (every Friday).

Contact Us

+1 5203365088
0917-806-9943
0920-967-8368

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Philippine Heart Center
8/F Medical and Arts Building
East Avenue, Quezon City, 1100

Physical Activity

SIMPLE PHYSICAL ACTIVITIES

REPETITIONS: 3 SET: 1 DAILY: 3 WEEKLY: 7

BREATHING EXERCISES

- Inhale through your nose.
- Hold for 3 seconds.
- Exhale through your lips (pursed).

SUPINE ANKLE PUMPS

- Begin lying on your back with your legs straight.
- Slowly pump your ankles by bending and straightening them.

TIP: Try to keep the rest of your legs relaxed while you move your ankles

SUPINE BRIDGE

- Begin lying on your back with your arms resting at your sides, your legs bent at the knees and your feet flat on the ground.
- Tighten your abdominals and slowly lift your hips off the floor into a bridge position, keeping your back straight.

TIP: Make sure to keep your trunk stiff throughout the exercise and your arms flat on the floor.

SEATED PURSED-LIP BREATHING

- Begin sitting upright in a chair.
- Breathe in through your nose, then blow out through pursed lips, as if you are blowing out a candle.

TIP: Make sure the exhalation is about twice as long as the inhalation.

SHOULDER ROLL BREATHING

- Begin sitting up tall in a comfortable position
- Breathe in through your nose and roll your shoulders forward and up towards your ears. Then, breathe out slowly through your mouth as you roll your shoulders backward and down. Repeat, drawing small circles with your shoulders as you breathe.

HORIZONTAL SHOULDER ABDUCTION & ADDUCTION

- Begin sitting upright.
- Raise your arms to shoulder height. Open your arms out to your sides, then bring your hands back together in front of you and repeat. Breathe in as you open your arms to the side and breathe out as you bring your arms back together.

SHOULDER FLEXION & EXTENSION

- Begin sitting upright.
- With your palms facing inward, lift your arms in front of you and above your head, inhaling as your arms come up. Then lower your arms, exhaling through your mouth as you bring them down and repeat.

SIT TO STAND

- Begin sitting upright with your feet flat on the ground underneath your knees.
- Move your shoulders and head over your toes, bring your knees forward, and allow your hips to come off the chair, then push down equally into both feet to stand up. Sit back down and repeat.

MARCH IN PLACE

- Begin in a standing upright position next to a counter or stable surface for support.
- Slowly lift one knee to waist height, hold briefly, then lower it back down and repeat with the opposite leg. Continue this movement, alternating legs.

TIP: Make sure to keep your balance and maintain an upright posture during the exercise.

HEEL RISES WITH COUNTER SUPPORT

- Begin in a standing upright position with your hands resting on a counter in front of you.
- Slowly raise your heels off the ground, hold briefly, then lower them back down and repeat.

PUSH THE WALL

- Begin in a standing upright position with your arms resting on a sturdy wall in front of you.
- Push the wall with both arms in alignment with your whole body.

STANDING BALANCE IN CORNER

- Begin standing in a corner with your feet shoulder width apart. Place a chair, your walker, or something sturdy in front of you.
- Hold your balance.

TIP: Touch the walls of the corner if you need to regain your balance. Gently pull your belly button in to engage your core and do not hold your breath during the exercise.

Basic Life Support (American Heart Association)

Appendix M

Simple Physical Activities

Wake UP Call :) Gising Gising Na

REPETITIONS: 3	SET: 1	DAILY: 3	WEEKLY: 7
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Start our day with Breathing exercises.
Inhale through your nose.
Hold for 3 secs.
Exhale through your lips (Pursed).

1. Supine Ankle Pumps

REPETITIONS: 3	SET: 1	DAILY: 3	WEEKLY: 7
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Setup

Begin lying on your back with your legs straight.

Movement

Slowly pump your ankles by bending and straightening them.

Tip

Try to keep the rest of your legs relaxed while you move your ankles.

(2) Supine Bridge

REPETITIONS: 3	SET: 1	DAILY: 3	WEEKLY: 7
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Setup

Begin lying on your back with your arms resting at your sides, your legs bent at the knees and your feet flat on the ground.

Movement

Tighten your abdominals and slowly lift your hips off the floor into a bridge position, keeping your back straight.

Tip

Make sure to keep your trunk stiff throughout the exercise and your arms flat on the floor.

(3) Seated Pursed Lip Breathing

REPETITIONS: 3	SET: 1	DAILY: 3	WEEKLY: 7
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Setup

Begin sitting upright in a chair.

Movement

Breathe in through your nose, then blow out through pursed lips, as if you are blowing out a candle.

Tip

Make sure the exhalation is about twice as long as the inhalation.

(4) Shoulder Roll Breathing

REPETITIONS: 3	SET: 1	DAILY: 3	WEEKLY: 7
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Setup

Begin sitting up tall in a comfortable position

Movement

Breathe in through your nose and roll your shoulders forward and up towards your ears. Then, breathe out slowly through your mouth as you roll your shoulders backward and down. Repeat, drawing small circles with your shoulders as you breathe.

Tip

Try to match your breathing with your shoulder movements. Breathe in as your shoulders come up and breathe out as your shoulders come down.

(5) Horizontal Shoulder Abduction and Adduction with Coordinated Breathing

REPETITIONS: 3	SET: 1	DAILY: 3	WEEKLY: 7
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Setup
Begin sitting upright.

Movement

Raise your arms to shoulder height. Open your arms out to your sides, then bring your hands back together in front of you and repeat. Breathe in as you open your arms to the side and breathe out as you bring your arms back together.

Tip

Try to keep your neck muscles relaxed and avoid shrugging your shoulders.

(6) Shoulder Flexion and Extension with Coordinated Breathing

REPETITIONS: 3	SET: 1	DAILY: 3	WEEKLY: 7
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Setup
Begin sitting upright.

Movement

With your palms facing inward, lift your arms in front of you and above your head, inhaling as your arms come up. Then lower your arms, exhaling through your mouth as you bring them down and repeat.

Tip

Make sure to keep your breath slow and steady and match the rhythm of your breathing with your arm movement.

(7) Sit to Stand

REPETITIONS: 3	SET: 1	DAILY: 3	WEEKLY: 7
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Setup

Begin sitting upright with your feet flat on the ground underneath your knees.

Movement

Move your shoulders and head over your toes, bring your knees forward, and allow your hips to come off the chair, then push down equally into both feet to stand up. Sit back down and repeat.

Tip: Make sure to keep your weight evenly distributed between both legs and try to keep your back straight throughout the exercise.

(8) March in Place

REPETITIONS: 3	SET: 1	DAILY: 3	WEEKLY: 7
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Setup

Begin in a standing upright position next to a counter or stable surface for support

Movement

Slowly lift one knee to waist height, hold briefly, then lower it back down and repeat with the opposite leg. Continue this movement, alternating legs.

Tip

Make sure to keep your balance and maintain an upright posture during the exercise.

(9) Heel rises with counter support

REPETITIONS: 3	SET:1	DAILY: 3	WEEKLY: 7
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Setup

Begin in a standing upright position with your hands resting on a counter in front of you.

Movement

Slowly raise your heels off the ground, hold briefly, then lower them back down and repeat.

(10) PUSH THE WALL

REPETITIONS: 3	SET:1	DAILY: 3	WEEKLY: 7
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Setup

Begin in a standing upright position with your arms resting on a sturdy wall in front of you.

Movement

Push the wall with your both arms in alignment with your whole body.

(11) Standing Balance in Corner (OPTIONAL)

REPETITIONS: : 3	SETS: 1	HOLD: 30	DAILY: 3	WEEKLY: 7
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Setup

Begin standing in a corner with your feet shoulder width apart. Place a chair, your walker, or something sturdy in front of you.

Movement

Hold your balance.

Tip

Touch the walls of the corner if you need to regain your balance. Gently pull your belly button in to engage your core and do not hold your breath during the exercise.

Appendix N

Instructions on Pedometer Use

Instructions on how to use the PEDOMETER. (*Mga Tagubilin sa kung paano gamitin ang Pedometer*).

1. Reset the counter at the time you wake up.
I-reset and counter sa oras ng paggising.
2. Place it in your arm when you start your day.
Ilagay sa iyong kamao kapag sinimulan mo na ang iyong araw.
3. Please write the number of steps you had before you go to bed. (You will also be reminded, through SMS / text, at 9pm daily.)
Mangyaring isulat ang bilang ng mga hakbang na mayroon ka bago matulog. (Mapapaalalahanan ka rin sa pamamagitan ng text alas nuwebe ng gabi.)
4. The pedometer will stay with you for 30 days.
Manatili sa iyo and pedometer sa loob ng 30 araw.
5. It is not water-resistant and shockproof.
Hindi ito gumagana sa tubig.
6. Please do not shake unnecessarily as it records the metallic ball bouncing inside the pedometer.
Mangyaring huwag yanigin ng hindi kinakailangan , dahil itinataala nito ang metal na bola na tumatalbog sa loob ng pedometer.

Appendix O

Good Clinical Practice Certificates

NIDA Clinical Trials Network

Certificate of Completion

is hereby granted to

MARY LORELEI MACAZO

to certify your completion of the six-hour required course on:

GOOD CLINICAL PRACTICE

MODULE:

Introduction
Institutional Review Boards
Informed Consent
Confidentiality & Privacy
Participant Safety & Adverse Events
Quality Assurance
The Research Protocol
Documentation & Record-Keeping
Research Misconduct
Roles & Responsibilities
Recruitment & Retention
Investigational New Drugs

STATUS:

N/A
Passed
Passed

Course Completion Date: 26 April 2021

CTN Expiration Date: 26 April 2024

Tracee Williams, Training Coordinator
NIDA Clinical Coordinating Center

Good Clinical Practice, Version 5, effective 03-Mar-2017

This training has been funded in whole or in part with Federal funds from the National Institute on Drug Abuse, National Institutes of Health, Department of Health and Human Services, under Contract No. HHSN27201201000024C.

Note:

GCP Certificate of Dr. Aldrin Calimag and Edreck Estioko submitted to PHC IERB

CURRICULUM VITAE

MARY LORELEI F. MACAZO
BSN RN MAN
12373 N Sutter Drive Unit 3 Marana Arizona, USA
Mobile: +1 (520) 3365088
Email: maryloirelei14@gmail.com

Relevant Quality Assurance and Quality Improvement Experiences

Selected as a core member of the King-Abdulaziz Medical City National Guard Health Affairs Quality Management team, representing the King-Abdulaziz Cardiac Center's QI, for the Joint Commission International Accreditation (JCIA) Quality Indicators. These are standardized, evidence-based measures with readily available hospital inpatient administrative data to measure and track clinical performance and outcomes relating to healthcare provisions. QPS.3 Monitor and track changes: Acute Coronary Syndrome and Congestive Heart Failure Medication Therapy.

Relevant Nursing Education Experiences

Carl Balita Review Center (CBRC) Manila, Philippines 2014-2016

National Reviewer for Philippine Nursing Licensure Board; Subjects Taught (Fundamentals of Nursing, Anatomy and Physiology, Therapeutic Nursing and Health Records). Teaches NCLEX Review: Subjects Taught (Cardiovascular, Pulmonary, Fundamentals of Nursing, Cardiac Rhythms Review, BLS and ACLS).

American Heart Association 2006-2016

Instructor, Basic Life Support
Instructor, Advance Cardiac Life Support

Centro-Escolar University Manila, Philippines (1996-1999)

Instructor I. Provide Clinical Preceptorship to Level III and IV BS Nursing students affiliated to San Lazaro Hospital (Infectious), V-Luna Hospital (Trauma), Polymedic hospital (MS) and Capitol Medical Center (ER). Engage in Classroom teaching : Acute Biologic Crisis and Primary Nursing Core subjects (Level IV).

Relevant Clinical Nursing Experiences

Travel PCU-RN November 2020 to Current

Accepts Crisis Response RN Job in different US States on a specified period of time. Close Critical care is needed to render nursing care to PCU/Stepdown Cardiovascular having broad telemetry and cardiovascular knowledge, skills and competency . Adheres strictly to policies and procedures of facility assigned. Responds to emergency situations following BLS, ACLS guidelines.

Cares for COVID and Covid Recovery cases. Facilities worked as follows:

FACILITY	BED CAPACITY	ROLE	DATE	LOCATION
University of California San Francisco	1290 L1 Trauma	CV-PCU	13 June to current	Parnassus, San Francisco
Lompoc Valley Medical Center	60	MS Telemetry	February 2024 to current	Lompoc California
Miami Valley Hospital	970 L1Trauma	Cardiac Stepdown	July 2023 to January 2024	Dayton OHIO
University of New Mexico Hospital	618 L1Trauma	PCU Medical	March - June 2023	Albuquerque New Mexico
Yuma Regional Medical Center	406 L4Trauma	Medical Surgical - Ortho	Nov 2022 – Feb 2023	Yuma Arizona
Cooper University Healthcare	635 L1Trauma	PCU - Float	Oct 2021 - Jan 2022	Camden, New Jersey
Duke University Hospital	989 L1Trauma	Cardiac Stepdown	June to Sept 2021	Durham, North Carolina
Pomona Medical Center	412 L2Trauma	PCU Telemetry COVID	Jan – May 2021	Pomona California
Eisenhower Medical Center	476 L4Trauma	PCU Telemetry COVID	Oct – Jan 2020	Palm Springs California
Banner University Hospital	649 L1Trauma	PCU Telemetry	July – Oct 2020	Phoenix Arizona
Southeast Baptist Medical Center	406 L4Trauma	PCU Telemetry	Feb – June 2020	Beaumont Texas
Banner del Webb Hospital	366 L3Trauma	PCU Telemetry	Nov 2019 – Feb 2020	Sun City Arizona

Tucson Medical Center Tucson , Arizona USA 2018 to 2020; Bed Capacity 600

Float Pool RN & Medical Surgical Telemetry Nurse : Promote patients' independence by establishing patient care goals and teaching patients and families to understand conditions, medications, and self-care skills. Relies on experience and judgment to plan and accomplish goals. Takes care of Adult Medical and Surgical Patients. New Case Handled : COVID 19 . Active Member: Wound Care Team

Northwest Medical Center Tucson, Arizona USA 2017-2019 Bed Capacity 300

Acts as a Telemetry nurse. Telemetry Nurses fall under the category of progressive care nurse, as defined by the American Association of Critical Care Nurses (AACN), caring for acutely and critically ill cardiovascular patients.

Philippine Heart Center Quezon City, Philippines (2016-2017): Reinstatement

Assign As Vascular (Out-Patient) and Wound Care Nurse. Contribution: Formalize an electronic Research sequel for the Vascular department using the Institutions' electronic system. (Baseline Nursing Orientation and awareness on VTE Risk screening, tool and management.

Kingabdulaziz Medical City National Guard Health Affairs Riyadh, Saudi Arabia (2004-2013): Bed Capacity 700

2004: Assigned to Adult Cardiology Ward Ratio 1:6, Acts as Charge Nurse and Preceptor to RN Orientees. Cases Handled Non-STEMI (ACS), Pre Valvular repair or replacement, Anticoagulation (oral and IV Heparin drips, Reopro), DM Control (Insulin drips). Exemplary Skills acquired: AHA BLS and ACLS. Bedside and Central Tele monitoring.

2005: Pioneered the opening of the Coronary Care Unit Ratio 1:4. Acts as Charge Nurse and Preceptor to RN Orientees (All Malaysian Nationals CCU trained). Spearheaded Staff Education in the Cardiac Adult Center.

2006: Cross-trained to Adult Cardiac Stepdown and been a part of the Adult Cardio-Vascular ICU Ratio 1:2 Handles Immediate post CABG, Valvular repair / replacement, patients with LVAD. Exemplary Skills learned: Mechanical Ventilation and weaning, Use of O2 supports, IABP, Chest tube insertion and removal, Suctioning, Central / CVP line monitoring and removal. IV Medication administration (Anti-arryhtemics, IV antibiotics, Insulin Drip, Inotropes (Dopamine, Dobutamine, Levophed, Epinephrine, Norepinephrine), Diuretics (Furosemide, Mannitol), Anti-hypertensives (Nitroprusside), Vasodilators (Nitroglycerine) and Electrolyte replacements (Potassium and Magnesium).

2007: Transferred to Medical Cardiac ICU; Ratio 1:3 Handles ACS (STEMI) and complicated Non STEMI cases. Exemplary Skills learned: Mechanical Ventilation and weaning, Use of O2 supports, IABP, Swan Ganz CO/CI Monitoring), Central / CVP line monitoring, Arterial and Venous sheaths care and removal, Fresenius CRRT Dialysis and bedside tele monitoring. Medication administration (Anti-arryhtemics, IV antibiotics, Insulin Drip, Inotropes (Dopamine, Dobutamine, Levophed, Epinephrine, Norepinephrine), Diuretics (Furosemide, Mannitol), Anti- hypertensives (Nitroprusside), Vasodilators (Nitroglycerine) and Electrolyte replacements (Potassium and Magnesium). Became an AHA BLS and ACLS active Instructor.

2008-2013: Promoted as a Clinical Resource Nurse (Educator). Spearheaded the Electronic Nursing (ICIP) and Physicians Documentation (Apollo) Cardiac PACS system. Facilitates interfacing, Radiology, Laboratory, Imaging / PET and Cardiac Cath lab into ICIP / Apollo e- systems. Consistently graded 98% to 100% for Documentation System by the Joint Commission International Accreditation from 2008-2012 (Re-accreditation). Achieved a 0% Medical Records Discharge and Operative Reports Summary Physicians Liability. Goal met: Once a patient is discharged; Records are fully completed, electronically signed by discharging MD and electronically delivered to the Medical Records Department. Same goes with the Op Report.

Prince Sultan Cardiac Center Riyadh, Saudi Arabia (2000-2002): Bed Capacity 174

Floor nurse to adult cardiovascular Nursing Ratio 1:6. Cases handled: Pre and post PCI. Non-STEMI cases, Valvular, Infectious. Exemplary skills acquired. Arterial and Venous sheath removal and monitoring post PCI cases, Central tele-monitoring. Worked in a multi-cultural environment ; ability to converse in Arabic language.

Philippine Heart Center Quezon City, Philippines (1991-1995): Bed Capacity 300

Novice RN climbed each step through the institutions career ladder program. Started in Service ward (MW/WW) with a ratio of 1:15. Floor nurse Handling cardiovascular adult cases: Pre-op Vascular, Valvular, Ischemic and patients with Cardiac Infectious cases. as a result of Served as an IMCU Nurse from 1992-1993 handles mostly Stroke cases as a result of uncontrolled hypertension, Diabetes Mellitus and Kidney insult. Exemplary skills learned EKG Rhythms, 12 lead EKG interpretation, Peritoneal dialysis, Continuous Bladder irrigation (CBI). A stepdown from Medical Intensive Unit. 1993-1995 Worked in Medical Intensive Care Unit. Mostly cardio- ischemic cases handling ACS (STEMI and NSTEMI) , Arrhythmic, Moderate to Severe Heart Failure. Exemplary skills learned EKG Rhythms, 12 lead EKG interpretation, Swan Ganz (CO/CI monitoring), CVP and Central line monitoring, IABP , TPM and PPM/ICD, Mechanical Ventilation and weaning. Use of various O2 support. IV Cannulation, Suctioning, Chest tube management (water seal) and Medication administration requiring Inotropes, Arrhythmic, Vasodilators, Diuretics, Mannitol, Insulin, Anti-hypertensives (Nitroprusside) and IV Antibiotics. Pioneer group in spearheading the ICU Staff Education re : Annual Case Study presentation: 1st Case presented Guillain-Barre Syndrome and Monthly Patient and Family Brigade as an act to involve the family to patient care .

Nursing Education:

Master of Arts in Nursing (Adult Health); 2024 Graduated
University of the Philippines Open University, Philippines
Master of Arts in Nursing : 1997, (33Units) Undergraduate
Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Maynila, General Luna St Manila, Philippines

Bachelor of Science in Nursing (3rd and 4th Year). Galang Medical Center and
Colleges (June 1988-1990) Sta. Cruz Manila, Philippines
Bachelor of Science in Nursing (1st and 2nd Year) Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng
Maynila (1986- April 1988) General Luna St Manila, Philippines

International Examinations:

IELTS (International English Language Testing System): Academic (2017)
National Council Licensure Examination (California Board): 2008
Saudi Council Licensure Examination (2000)

Memberships

American Nursing Association (2017 to Current)
Association of Nursing Service Administrators of the Philippines (ANSAP) (2016)
Critical Care Nurses Association of the Philippines, Inc. (1992-1996)
Philippine Nurses Association (1991)

Computer Literacy

Electronic Medical Record: Apollo Lumedx (Clinical Data Intelligence), *Philips* IntelliVue
Clinical Information Portfolio (*ICIP*), EPIC, CERNER, Medhost
MS Office Applications 2003/2007/2010/2016
Microsoft Word, Excel, Power Point, Outlook, Access-Basic, Visio, Publisher
Statistical Analysis: SPSS 7,8

Certifications

- American Heart Association Certification for Advance Cardiac Life Support (2022)
- American Heart Association Certification for Basic Life Support (2022)
- Department of Health Nurse Certification Program (Philippines) Level III Cardiovascular Nursing (2017)
- American Heart Association Certification for Advance Cardiac Life Support Instructor (2006 to 2015)
- American Heart Association Certification for Adult Basic Life Support Instructor (2005 to 2016)